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Appendix A.1.			
All Awards to Date			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
<u>May 2005 Awards</u>			
<u>Postdoctoral Fellows</u>			
Fisher, Kirsten	Univ of California - Berkeley	The phylogenomics of desiccation tolerance in the land plants	Sept 2005
Granek, Joshua	Johns Hopkins Univ	Comparative genomic studies of the sequences responsible for the regulation of gene expression	Aug 2005
Hazkani-Covo, Einat	Tel-Aviv University	Numt variation in metazoan genomes: gain, loss, duplication and possible function	March 2006
Hereford, Joe	Floria St Univ, Tallahassee	Adaptive divergence between natural populations	Sept 2005
Kidd, David	Univ of St. Andrews, UK	Phylogeographical information science: linking phylogenies and earth history	Oct 2005
Price, Samantha	Univ of Virginia	Cetartiodactyl evolution: understanding the evolutionary transition from the terrestrial to the aquatic biome	Nov 2005
Zanne, Amy	Masaryk Univ, Brno, Czech Rep	Hydraulic efficiency and safety: Do tradeoffs have an evolutionary basis in the rosids?	Aug 2006 w/NSF postdoc fellowship; NESCent postdoc begins May 2007.
Zwickl, Derrick	Univ of Texas, Austin	Implementation of a wide range of codon and amino acid models in Bayesian phylogenetic software	Jan 2006
<u>Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
Clamp, John	North Carolina Central Univ	1) Attracting minority graduate applicants into careers in evolutionary biology and 2) develop research in molecular systematics	12 mos, July 2005-June 2006
Cronk, Quentin	Univ of British Columbia, Vancouver	Creating an evolutionary dataspace for plants: allowing phylogenetic, morphological and gene ontologies to collide gracefully	11-mo, Oct 2005-Aug 2006
Eyre-Walker, Adam	Univ of Sussex, UK	1) distribution of fitness effects of new mutations and 2) the rate of adaptive evolution	12-mo, Oct 2005-Sept 2006
Lewis, Paul	Univ of Connecticut	Incorporation of all maximum likelihood phylogenetic analyses currently performed by PAUP*4b10 into Phycas.	5-mo, Jan-May 2006 (funded by CIPRES)
McMillan, Owen	Univ of Puerto Rico - Rio Pedras	Relational evolutionary database for <i>Heliconius</i> butterflies	12-mo, Sept 2005-Aug 2006
<u>Catalysis Meetings</u>			
Glor, Richard	Univ of California - Davis	Biological diversification on the West Indian Archipelago	July 2006, Dominican Republic
Proulx, Stephen	Univ of Oregon	Integrated studies of genetic networks: A new evolutionary synthesis	Jan 2006, Marathon Key
Schmitt, Daniel	Duke Univ	Primate Fossil Analysis	Feb 2006
<u>Working Groups</u>			
Donoghue, Michael	Yale Univ	Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere	March 2006

All Awards to Date			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
Kalisz, Susan	Univ of Pittsbburgh	Understanding the paradox of mixed mating in flowering plants	April 2006
Mabee, Paula	Univ of South Dakota	Towards an integrated database for fish evolution	Feb 2006
<u>March 2006 Awards</u>			
<u>Postdoctoral Fellows</u>			
Burleigh, Gordon	Univ of California - Davis	A Phylogenetic Database for Comparative Biology in Land Plants	Nov 2006
Ganapathy, Ganeshkumar	Univ of Texas - Austin	New DCM Methods for ML, and Pattern Identification in Biogeography	Dec 2006
Hoeksema, Jason	Univ of California - Santa Cruz	What is the Relative Importance of Biotic vs. Abiotic Local Adaptation?	July 2006
Hopkins, Samantha	Univ of California - Berkeley	The Evolution of Mammalian Fossoriality: Causes and Consequences	Aug 2006
McCall, Lauren W.	Univ Cambridge	Building a Framework for the Study of Cultural Evolution	Jan 2007
Sidlauskas, Brian	Univ Chicago	Understanding Parallel Morphological Diversification in Sister Fish Faunas	Sept 2006
<u>Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
Eernisse, Douglas	Calif St Univ - Fullerton	Chiton Phylogeny and Comparative Phylogeography	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
Fail, Jr., Joseph	Johnson C. Smith Univ	Designing and Teaching an Evolution Curriculum for Elementary Students	12-mos, Sept 2006 - Aug 2007
Otto, Sarah	Univ of British Columbia	A Community Approach to Evolutionary Theory	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
Whitlock, Michael	Univ of British Columbia	Evolution in a Spatial Context: A Synthesis of Theory and Review	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
<u>Catalysis Meetings</u>			
Govindaraju, Raju	Boston Univ School of Med	Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations: Medical, Genetic and Behavioral Implications	~ Mar - June 2007
Hughes, Kimberly	Univ of Illinois	Developing New Model Systems for Evolutionary Genomics Using Poeciliid Fishes	May 2007
Kocher, Thomas	Univ of New Hampshire	Genomic Approaches to the Study of Adaptive Radiation	April 2007
Yoder, Anne	Duke Univ	Patterns of Biodiversity in Madagascar	June 2006
<u>Working Groups</u>			
Jungck, John R	BioQUEST Curriculum Consortium, Beloit College	Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in AcTION	Dec 2006
Leebens-Mack, Jim	Penn State Univ	The Plant EvoGenomics Working Group: Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics	Sept 2006
Noor, Mohamed	Duke Univ	Proposal to Develop a Novel Journal Concept for Evolutionary Meta-Analyses	June 2006
Oakley, Todd	Univ of California - Santa Barbara	Fossil and Molecular Estimates of Divergence Times for the Tree of Life: Database and Synthesis	Sept 2006

All Awards to Date			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
<u>Triangle Working Group</u>			
Clarke, Julia	North Carolina St Univ	Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular Biology and Paleontology	May 2006
<i>September 2006 Awards</i>			
<u>Catalysis Meetings</u>			
Fred Gould, S. Sinkins and D. Hartl	North Carolina St Univ, Oxford, and Harvard	Selfish DNA and the Genetic Control of Vector-borne Diseases	Oct 2007
Roy Plotnick	Univ of Illinois at Chicago	Origins and Evolution of Chemoreception	June 2007
<u>Working Groups</u>			
Casey Bergman, Martin Kreitman, and Manolis Dermitzakis	Univ of Manchester, Univ of Chicago, and The Wellcome Trust Sanger Inst, UK	Synthesizing Computational Resources for Cis-regulatory Molecular Evolution.	Mar 2007
Joel Cracraft and Mark Siddall	American Museum of Natural History	Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography	
Paul Magwene and David Houle	Duke Univ and Florida St Univ	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks	Feb/Mar 2007
Jonathan Payne, Jennifer Stempien and Michal Kowalewski	Stanford Univ and Virginia Tech	Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology	Jan/Feb 2007
Arlin Stoltzfus and Rutger Vos	Center for Advanced Res in Biotech and Simon Fraser Univ	Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis	Apr 2007
Karen Strier, Susan Alberts and Patricia Wright	Univ of Wisconsin - Madison, Duke Univ, and State Univ of NY - Stony Brook	Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories	Aug 2007
<u>Triangle Working Group</u>			
March Uyenoyama and Alade Tokuta	Duke Univ and North Carolina Central Univ	Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression	Dec 2006

Appendix A.2.			
Current Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Visiting Scientists			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
<u>Postdoctoral Fellows</u>			
Burleigh, Gordon	Univ of California - Davis	A Phylogenetic Database for Comparative Biology in Land Plants	Nov 2006
Fisher, Kirsten	Univ of California - Berkeley	The phylogenomics of desiccation tolerance in the land plants	Sept 2005
Ganapathy, Ganeshkumar	Univ of Texas - Austin	New DCM Methods for ML, and Pattern Identification in Biogeography	Dec 2006
Granek, Joshua	Johns Hopkins Univ	Comparative genomic studies of the sequences responsible for the regulation of gene expression	Aug 2005
Hazkani-Covo, Einat	Tel-Aviv University	Numt variation in metazoan genomes: gain, loss, duplication and possible function	March 2006
Hereford, Joe	Floria St Univ, Tallahassee	Adaptive divergence between natural populations	Sept 2005
Hoeksema, Jason	Univ of California - Santa Cruz	What is the Relative Importance of Biotic vs. Abiotic Local Adaptation?	July 2006
Hopkins, Samantha	Univ of California - Berkeley	The Evolution of Mammalian Fossoriality: Causes and Consequences	Aug 2006
Kidd, David	Univ of St. Andrews, UK	Phylogeographical information science: linking phylogenies and earth history	Oct 2005
McCall, Lauren W.	Univ Cambridge	Building a Framework for the Study of Cultural Evolution	Jan 2007
Price, Samantha	Univ of Virginia	Cetartiodactyl evolution: understanding the evolutionary transition from the terrestrial to the aquatic biome	Nov 2005
Sidlauskas, Brian	Univ Chicago	Understanding Parallel Morphological Diversification in Sister Fish Faunas	Sept 2006
Zanne, Amy	Masaryk Univ, Brno, Czech Rep	Hydraulic efficiency and safety: Do tradeoffs have an evolutionary basis in the rosids?	Aug 2006 w/NSF postdoc fellowship; NESCent postdoc begins May 2007.
Zwickl, Derrick	Univ of Texas, Austin	Implementation of a wide range of codon and amino acid models in Bayesian phylogenetic software	Jan 2006
<u>Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
Eernisse, Douglas	Calif St Univ - Fullerton	Chiton Phylogeny and Comparative Phylogeography	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
Fail, Jr., Joseph	Johnson C. Smith Univ	Designing and Teaching an Evolution Curriculum for Elementary Students	12-mos, Sept 2006 - Aug 2007
Otto, Sarah	Univ of British Columbia	A Community Approach to Evolutionary Theory	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
Whitlock, Michael	Univ of British Columbia	Evolution in a Spatial Context: A Synthesis of Theory and Review	9-mos, Sept 2006 - May 2007
<u>Visiting Scholars with NESCent Funding</u>			
Jones, Clara B.	Fayetteville State Univ	Solving the Alouatta paradox: From polygyny to polygynandry	April 2006-March 2008
Ramirez, Martin	Natural Sciences Museum, Argentina	Connecting best practices experiences and user interface development for morphological databases	June 2006

Current Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Visiting Scientists			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
<u>Visiting Scholars without NESCent Funding</u>			
Roth, V. Louise	Duke Univ	Squirrels as models in macroevolution; Scaling	Jan-Dec 2006
<u>Triangle Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
Gensel, Patricia	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	Evolutionary relationships of Devonian age fossil plants	Jan-June 2006
Muse, Spencer	North Carolina St Univ	Analysis of genetic data	Sept 2005-Aug 2006
Servedio, Maria	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	Analysis of factors that determine the occurrence of speciation and reinforcement	Sept-Dec 2006
Willis, John	Duke Univ	Evolutionary genomics and bioinformatics of Mimulus, a developing model system for studies of plant adaptation and speciation	Sept-Dec 2006
<u>At-Large Members of the Operations Committee</u>			
Gensel, Patricia	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	N/A	Jan-Dec 2006
Noor, Mohammed	Duke Univ	N/A	Jan-June 2006
Wiegmann, Brian	North Carolina St Univ	N/A	Jan-Dec 2006
Wray, Greg	Duke Univ	N/A	July-Dec 2006

Appendix A.3.

NESCent Seminar Series 2006			
Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Jan-13-2006	Jason Stajich	Graduate Student, Duke Univ	BioPerl and Comparative Fungal Genomics
Jan-17-2006	Dr. Peter Keightley	Institute of Evolutionary Biology, Univ of Edinburgh, UK	Genome-wide Deleterious Mutation in Nematodes and Fruit Flies-causes and Evolutionary Consequences
Jan-20-2006	Dr. John Clamp	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, North Carolina Central Univ	Recruiting Minority Graduate Students into Evolutionary Biology
Jan-27-2006	Erin Heath	American Institute of Biological Sciences, Washington, DC	Media Training for Scientists
Feb-10-2006	Dr. Quentin Cronk	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Univ British Columbia, Canada	Black Cottonwood as a Model for the Ecogenomics of Trees
Feb-17-2006	Dr. Kathleen Smith	NESCent Director, Duke Univ	Reproductive Patterns and the Evolution of Development in Mammals
Feb-24-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Session 1 - Learning Theories, Learning Styles
Mar-03-2006	Dr. Adam Eyre-Walker	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, University of Sussex, UK	How Did We and Will We Survive - An Investigation into the Rates and Fitness Effects of Mutations in Humans
Mar-10-2006	Dr. David Kidd	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Phylogeographical Information Systems: Linking Phylogenies to Earth History
Mar-17-2006	Dr. John Clamp	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, North Carolina Central Univ	Molecular Systematics and Phylogeny of Peritrich Ciliates
Mar-24-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Session 2 - Critical Thinking and the Nature of Science
Mar-31-2006	Dr. Josh Granek	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Exploring the Origins of the 1918 Influenza
Apr-07-2006	Dr. Owen McMillan	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Univ Puerto Rico	Towards a Comparative Genomic Understanding of Mimicry in Heliconius
Apr-21-2006	Dr. Patricia Gensel	NESCent Triangle Sabbatical Scholar, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	Structural and Architectural Innovation in Early Devonian Basal Euphyllophytes, Probable Precursors to Fern and Seed Plant Lineages
Apr-28-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Session 3 - Planning Your First Course
May-05-2006	Dr. Spencer Muse	NESCent Triangle Sabbatical Scholar, North Carolina State Univ	Silent Substitution Rates are Variable Within Genes
May-12-2006	Dr. Samantha Price	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Cetartiodactyla: Phylogeny, Life History and Extinction
May-19-2006	Dr. V. Louise Roth	Associate Professor of Biology, Duke Univ	Squirrel Phylogenies as Chronometers for Historical Biogeography

NESCent Seminar Series 2006			
Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
May-26-2006	Dr. Brian Rybarczyk	Dir of Educational Support Programs, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	Session 4 - Engaging Students: Active Learning, Case-Based Learning, and Other Methods
Jun-02-2006	Dr. Greg Gibson	NESCent Assoc Dir, North Carolina State Univ	Canalization and Cryptic Variation
Jun-09-2006	Mike Dickison	Graduate Student, Duke Univ	Information Design in Biology
Jul-07-2006	Dr. Einat Hazkani-Covo	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Evolution of Nuclear Mitochondrial Pseudogenes (Numts) in Primates
Jul-14-2006	Molly Starback & Elizabeth Johnson	Duke Office of Postdoctoral Services, President of the Duke Univ Postdoctoral Assoc	Services and Opportunities for Postdocs
Jul-21-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Session 5 - Student Involvement: Group Projects, Self-Directed Learning and Learning Communities
Jul-28-2006	None		
Aug-04-2006	Dr. David Kidd	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Introducing the "NESCent Camel Challenge"
Aug-11-2006	Dr. Adam Eyre-Walker	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Univ of Sussex, UK	Use & Abuse of Tajima's D, Slightly Advantageous Mutations; the Other Side of the Nearly Neutral Theory
Aug-18-2006	Dr. Jim Balhoff	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	A Discussion of Workflow Software for Evolutionary Biology
Aug-25-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Session 6 - Teaching With Technology, Teaching Via VTC
Sep-01-2006	Jason Hoeksema	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	How Should Local Adaptation Be Studied?
Sep-08-2006	Dr. Joel Kingsolver	NESCent Assoc Dir, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	Real Evolution Has Curves: Understanding Function-Valued Traits
Sep-22-2006	Dr. Greg Wray	NESCent Operations Committee, Duke Univ	Finding The Mutations That Make Us Human: From Genome to Nucleotide
Sep-29-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Applying for Faculty Positions in Evolution: An Informal Discussion with NESCent Sabbatical Scholars and Postdoctoral Fellows
Oct-06-2006	Dr. Sally Otto	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Univ of British Columbia, Canada	Genomic Structure and Rates of Evolution
Oct-13-2006	Dr. Brian Sidlauskas	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Hyperdisparate Headstanders and Static Slime-Suckers: Uncovering Rates and Trends of Morphological Diversification in Tropical Characin Fishes
Oct-20-2006	Dr. Patrick Phillips	Center of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Univ of Oregon	Sex, Death and the Evolution of Nematode Mating Systems
Oct-20-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub and Ahrash Bissell	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Session 7 - Testing, Assessment and Grading

NESCent Seminar Series 2006			
Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Oct-25-2006	Dr. Claude dePamphilis	Associate Professor of Biology, Penn State	Genome Evolution in Parasitic Plants: New Genomes, Surprising Findings
Oct-27-2006	Dr. Brian Wiegmann	NESCent Operations Committee, NCSU	Multigene Phylogenetics of Flies in the Tree of Life
Nov-03-2006	Dr. Douglas Eernisse	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Calif St Univ	Will Comparing Phylogenetic and Phylogeographic Patterns of West Coast Chitons and Limpets Help Explain Spectacular Parallel Radiations?
Nov-10-2006	Dr. Maria Servedio	NESCent Triangle Sabbatical Scholar, UNC-CH	Male Mate Choice During Polygyny
Nov-17-2006	Drs. Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins	NESCent EOG Postdoc Development Program	Session 8 – Classroom Management, Dealing With Difficult Students
Dec-01-2006	Dr. Michael Whitlock	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Univ British Columbia, Canada	Evolution in a Spatial Context
Dec-08-2006	Dr. Joseph Fail, Jr.	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Johnson C. Smith Univ	The Importance of Early Education in Evolution, its Current State in North Carolina, and a Suggested Approach for Teaching Evolution to Elementary Students
Dec-15-2006	Dr. Samantha Hopkins	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	Down the Rabbit Hole: Convergence and Dead-End Adaptation in the Evolution of Fossoriality
Jan-12-2007	Lisa Horth	Assistant Professor of Biological Sciences, Old Dominion Univ	
Jan-19-2007	Dr. Patricia Gensel	NESCent Operations Committee, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	
Jan-26-2007	Dr. Amy Zanne	NESCent Postdoc Fellow	
Feb-02-2007	Dr. Clara B. Jones	NESCent Sabbatical Scholar, Fayetteville State Univ	

Appendix A.4.					
List of Meetings					
January 1, 2006 - November 30, 2006					
Date	Group Leaders	Meeting Name	Location	# Attendees	Type
January 12-13, 2006	Kingsolver, Joel	Scientific Advisory Bd	NESCent	15	Advisory
January 13-16, 2006	Proulx, Stephen Hahn, Matthew Promislow, Daniel	Integrated Studies of Genetics	Marathon, Florida	35	Catalysis
January 18, 2006	McMillan, Owen Vision, Todd	GMOD meeting	NESCent	6	Informatics
January 30-31, 2006	Peet, Robert	SEEK Taxon Group	NESCent	12	Hosted
January 31-February 3, 2006	Hobern, Donald Belbin, Lee Pereira, Ricardo	GUID-1 (Globally Unique Identifiers)	NESCent	35	Hosted
February 16-19, 2006	Schmitt, Daniel	Primate Fossil Analysis	NESCent	35	Catalysis
March 3, 2006	Nijhout, Fred	NIH Proposal	NESCent	10	Hosted
March 5-9, 2006	Donoghue, Michael Manos, Paul	Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere	NESCent	15	Work Group
March 9-10, 2006	Hackett, Shannon	AToL Early Bird Meeting	NESCent	12	Hosted
March 10, 2006	Shaw, Jon	AToL Reception	NESCent	75	Reception
April 8-11, 2006	Mabee, Paula Westerfield, Monte	Towards an Integrated Database for Fish Evolution	NESCent	12	Work Group
April 14-15, 2006	Schaal, Barbara	Senior Advisory Board	NESCent	12	Advisory
April 20-21, 2006	Gibson, Greg Jenkins, Kristin Weintraub, Jory	Evolutionary Education at Historically Minority Universities	NESCent	15	Education
April 21-26, 2006	Kalisz, Susan Johnston, Mark	Mixed Mating in Plants	NESCent	10	Work Group
May 18, 2006	Clarke, Julia Nagalingum, Nathalie Weigmann, Brian	Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular biology and Paleontology	Museum of Natural Sciences, Raleigh	17	Triangle Work Group
June 4-6, 2006	Noor, Mohamed Servedio, Maria	Development of a Novel Journal Concept for Evolutionary Meta-Analyses	NESCent	10	Work Group
June 12-16, 2006	Yoder, Anne Kremens, Claire	Patterns of Biodiversity in Madagascar	NESCent	30	Catalysis
June 14, 2006	Tang, Jijun	Phylogenetic Analysis with Complex Genome Rearrangement	NESCent	8	Hosted
June 29-30, 2006	Cain, Scott	GMOD	NESCent	35	Hosted
July 5-9, 2006	Glor, Rich Losos, Jonathan Ricklefs, Robert	Biological Diversification West Indian Archipelago	Punta Cana, Dominican Republic	30	Catalysis
July 10-12, 2006	Gibson, Greg Jenkins, Kristin Weintraub, Jory	Evolution Education	NESCent	20	Education
August 23-26, 2006	Gensel, Patricia	Taxonomic Database for Paleobiologists	NESCent	30	Hosted
September 6, 2006	Kingsolver, Joel	Scientific Advisory Board	NESCent	15	Advisory
September 6-10, 2006	Oakley, Todd	Fossil & Molecular Estimates of Divergence Times for the Tree of Life	NESCent	10	Work Group
September 17-21, 2006	Leebens-Mack, Jim Brenner, Eric Vision, Todd	The Plant EvoGenetics Working Group: Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics	NESCent	16	Work Group
November 11-14, 2006	Mabee, Paula Westerfield, Monte	Towards an Integrated Database for Fish Evolution	NESCent	12	Work Group
November 17, 2006	Clarke, Julia Nagalingum, Nathalie Weigmann, Brian	Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular Biology and Paleontology	NESCent	17	Triangle Work Group
Other Provost Supported Activities					
May 8-9, 2006	Schindel, David	Recovering DNA from Formalin Fixed Biological Samples	Washington, DC	15	Co-Sponsored
July 2006	Alroy, John	Paleobiology Database Summer Course	Santa Barbara, CA	15	Co-Sponsored

Appendix A.5.

Participant Lists - NESCent Sponsored Meetings December 1, 2005 – November 30, 2006

Advisory Meetings

January 13 - 15, 2006

**Science Advisory Board
Coordinator: Joel Kingsolver**

Participants:

Lisa Donovan	University of Georgia
Catherine Graham	State University of New York, Stony Brook
Elizabeth Hadly	Stanford University
Laura Katz	Smith College
Thomas Kaufmann	Indiana University
Junhyong Kim	University of Pennsylvania
Joel Kingsolver	NESCent
Hirohisa Kishino	University of Tokyo
Jonathan Losos	Washington University in St. Louis
Joe Neigel	University of Louisiana
Sally Otto	University of British Columbia
Kathleen Smith	NESCent
Paul Turner	Yale University
Peter Wagner	The Field Museum
Peter Wainwright	University of California
Katherine Willis	University of Oxford
Marlene Zuk	University of California - Riverside

April 13 – 15, 2006

**Senior Advisory Board
Coordinator: Kathleen Smith
Chair: Barbara Schall**

Participants:

Scott Edwards	Harvard University
David Hillis	University of Texas
David Jablonski	University of Chicago
Elizabeth Kellogg	University of Missouri-St. Louis
Emília Martins	Indiana University
Lisa Nagy	University of Arizona
Jim Reichman	University of California, Santa Barbara
Barbara Schall	Washington University
Simon Tavaré	University of Southern California

September 6, 2006

**Science Advisory Board
Coordinator: Joel Kingsolver**

Participants:

Lisa Donovan	University of Georgia
Catherine Graham	State University of New York, Stony Brook
Elizabeth Hadly	Stanford University
Laura Katz	Smith College
Thomas Kaufmann	Indiana University
Junhyong Kim	University of Pennsylvania
Joel Kingsolver	NESCent
Hirohisa Kishino	University of Tokyo
Jonathan Losos	Washington University in St. Louis
Joe Neigel	University of Louisiana
Sally Otto	University of British Columbia
Kathleen Smith	NESCent
Paul Turner	Yale University
Peter Wagner	The Field Museum
Peter Wainwright	University of California
Katherine Willis	University of Oxford
Marlene Zuk	University of California - Riverside

Catalysis Meetings

January 13 -16, 2006

**Integrated Studies of Genetic Networks: A New
Evolutionary Synthesis
Catalysis Meeting**

**Coordinators: Stephen Proulx
Daniel Promislow
Matthew Hahn**

Participants:

Christina Burch	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Michael Costanzo	University of Toronto
Doug Green	St. Jude Children's Research Hospital
Zhenglong Gu	Stanford University
Matthew Hahn	Indiana University
Thomas Hansen	Florida State University
David Houle	Florida State University
King Jordan	National Institutes of Health
Caner Kazanci	University of Georgia
Andrew Kern	University of California - Davis
Jason Lieb	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Paul Magwene	Duke University
Monica Medina	University of California - Merced
Ron Milo	Weizmann Institute
Armin Moczek	Indiana University

Balazs Papp	University of Manchester
Patrick Phillips	University of Oregon
Adam Porter	Amherst
Daniel Promislow	University of Georgia
Stephen Proulx	Iowa State University
Matt Rockman	Princeton University
Jeff Sturkey	NESCent
Sarah Teichmann	MRC Cambridge University
Henrique Teotonio	Gulbankian Institute
Shripad Tuljapurkar	Stanford University
Andreas Wagner	University of New Mexico
Jory Weintraub	NESCent

February 16 -19, 2006

**Behavioral Reconstruction in Paleoanthropology
Catalysis Meeting
Coordinator: Daniel Schmitt**

Participants:

David Begun	University of Toronto
John Cant	University of Puerto Rico
Matt Cartmill	Duke University
Steve Churchill	Duke University
Bert Covert	University of Colorado
Marian Dagosto	Northwestern University
Brigitte Demes	Stony Brook University
Dan Gebo	Northern Illinois University
Ken Glander	Duke University
Aryeh Grossman	Evolutionary Anthropology Journal
Mark Hamrick	Medical College of Georgia
Terry Harrison	New York University
Andrew Hill	Yale University
Kevin D. Hunt	Indiana University
Clifford J. Jolly	New York University
Rich Kay	Duke University
Jay Kelley	University of Illinois
Susan G. Larson	Stony Brook University
Pierre Lemelin	University of Alberta
William McGraw	Ohio State University
Masato Nakatsukasa	Osaka University
Michael Platt	Duke University
Brian Richmond	George Washington University
Cordelia Rose	Smithsonian Institution
Mike Rose	New Jersey Medical School
Chris Ruff	Johns Hopkins University
Daniel Schmitt	Duke University
Jean E. Turnquist	University of Puerto Rico
Chris Vinyard	Northeastern Ohio Medical College
Alan Walker	Pennsylvania State University

Christine Wall
Carol Ward
Steven Ward
Roshna Wunderlich

Duke University
University of Missouri, Columbia
Northeastern Ohio Medical College
James Madison University

June 13 – 17, 2006

**Patterns of Biodiversity in Madagascar
Catalysis Meeting
Coordinators: Anne Yoder
Claire Kremen**

Participants:

Kobi Abdul-Salim
Peter Beerli
Bart Buyck
Allison Cameron
Brian Fisher
John Flynn
David Krause
Claire Kremen
David Lees
Atte Moilanen
Peter Morin
Craig Moritz
Mike Nowak
Eric Rakotoarisoa
Achille Raselimanana
Chris Raxworthy
Amy Russell
George Schatz
Jeff Thorne
Miguel Vences
David Vieties
Anne Yoder
Michelle Zjhra

Ohio State University
Florida State University
National Museum of Natural History
University of California - Berkeley
California Academy of Sciences
American Museum of Natural History
Stony Brook University
University of California - Berkeley
Natural History Museum - London
University of Helsinki
Rutgers University
University of California - Berkeley
Duke University
Yale University
Duke University
American Museum of Natural History
University of Arizona
Missouri Botanical Garden
North Carolina State University
University of Amsterdam
University of California - Berkeley
Duke University
Georgia Southern University

July 5-9, 2006

**Biological Diversification in the West Indian Archipelago
Catalysis Meeting
Punta Cana, Dominican Republic
Coordinators: Richard Glor
Jonathan Losos
Robert Ricklefs**

Participants:

Eldredge Bermingham
Sarah Crews
Cliff Cunningham
Daryl Domning

Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, PANAMA
University of California, Berkeley
Duke University
Howard University

Brian Farrell	Harvard University
Rosemary Gillespie	University of California, Berkeley
Richard Glor	University of California, Davis
Alan Graham	Missouri Botanical Garden
Blair Hedges	Pennsylvania State University
Michael Hellberg	Louisiana State University
Hope Hollocher	Notre Dame University
Manuel Iturralde-Vinent	Museo Nacional de Historia Natural, CUBA
Robert Jansen	University of Texas
Jason Knouft	University of Colorado, Boulder
Jonathan Losos	Washington University
Ross MacPhee	American Museum of Natural History
Anita Malhotra	University of Wales, UNITED KINGDOM
Paul Mann	University of Texas, Austin
Simon Mitchell	University of the West Indies, Mona, JAMAICA
Santiago Munoz	Dominican Geological Service
David Penney	University of Manchester, UNITED KINGDOM
Susan Perkins	American Museum of Natural History
Robert Ricklefs	University of Missouri, St. Louis
Carlos Rodriguez	University of Santo Domingo, DOMINICAN REPUBLIC
Eugenio Santiago-Valentin	University of Puerto Rico, PUERTO RICO
Christopher Schneider	Boston University
Roger Thorpe	University of Wales, UNITED KINGDOM
Jeff Sturkey	NESCent
Jory Weintraub	NESCent

Working Group Meetings

March 5 – 9, 2006

**Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere
Working Group
Coordinators: Michael Donoghue
Paul Manos**

Participants:

Michael Donoghue	Yale University
Peter Fritsch	California Academy of Sciences
Jianhua Li	Harvard University
Steven Manchester	Florida Museum of Natural History
Paul Manos	Duke University
Richard Milne	University of Edinburgh
Richard Ree	Field Museum of Natural History
Susanne Renner	University of Munich
Bob Ricklefs	University of Missouri - St. Louis
Hallie Sims	University of Iowa
Stephen Smith	Yale University
Jeff Thorne	North Carolina State University
Jun Wen	Smithsonian Institute
Jenny Xiang	North Carolina State University

April 8 - 11, 2006

**Towards an Integrated Database for Fish Evolution
Working Group**

**Coordinators: Paula Mabee
Monte Westerfield**

Participants:

Gloria Arratia	University of South Dakota
Stan Blum	California Academy of Sciences
Miles Coburn	John Carroll University
Mark Gibson	Berkeley Livermore Laboratory
Melissa Haendel	University of Oregon
Eric Hilton	Field Museum of Natural History
John Lundberg	Academy of Natural Sciences
Carol Lushbough	University of South Dakota
Paula Mabee	University of South Dakota
Rick Mayden	St. Louis University
Peter Midford	University of Michigan
Chris Mungall	Howard Hughes Medical Institute
Nelson Rios	Tulane University
Monte Westerfield	University of Oregon

April 21 – 26, 2006

**Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating in
Flowering Plants**

**Working Group
Coordinators: Susan Kalisz
Mark Johnston**

Participants:

Christopher Eckert	Queens University
Elizabeth Elle	Simon Fraser University
Monica Geber	Cornell University
Carol Goodwillie	East Carolina University
Mark Johnston	Dalhousie University
Susan Kalisz	University of Pittsburgh
John Kelley	University of Kansas
David Moeller	University of Minnesota
Emmanuelle Porcher	University of California, San Diego
Richard Ree	Field Museum of Natural History
Risa Sargent	University of British Columbia
Alice Winn	Florida State University

June 4 – 6, 2006

**Proposal to Develop a Novel Journal Concept for
Evolutionary Meta-Analyses**

**Working Group
Coordinators: Mohamed Noor
Maria Servidio**

Participants:

Robb Brumfield	Louisiana State University
Rick Harrison	Cornell University
Hopi Hoekstra	University of California - San Diego
Catriona MacCallum	Public Library of Science
Mohamed Noor	Duke University
Charlie Nunn	Max Planck Institute
Jim Regetz	University of California - Santa Barbara
Gil Rosenthal	Texas A & M University
Maria Servedio	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Mario Vallejo-Marin	Duke University

July 10-12, 2006**Evolution Education Working Group****Coordinators: Greg Gibson****Kristin Jenkins****Jory Weintraub****Participants:**

Brian Alters	Evolution Education Research Centre, McGill University
Alan Berkowitz	Institute of Ecosystem Studies
Rodger Bybee	Biological Sciences Curriculum Study
Judy Diamond	University of Nebraska State Museum
Sam Donovan	University of Pittsburgh
Margaret Evans	University of Michigan
Kristen Fisher	NESCent
Douglas Futuyma	State University of New York - Stony Brook
Yolanda George	American Association for the Advancement of Science
Greg Gibson	NESCent
Kristin Jenkins	NESCent
John Jungck	Beloit College and BioQUEST
Jay Labov	National Academies
Dennis Liu	Howard Hughes Medical Institute
Susan Musante	American Institute of Biological Sciences
Craig Nelson	Indiana University
Richard O'Grady	American Institute of Biological Sciences
Rob Pennock	Michigan State University
Jenn Piascik	North Carolina State University
Sam Price	NESCent
Malcolm Schug	University of North Carolina - Greensboro
Judy Scotchmoor	University of California Museum of Paleontology
Eugenie Scott	National Center for Science Education
Kathleen Smith	NESCent
Mark Terry	The Northwest School
Gordon Uno	University of Oklahoma
Jory Weintraub	NESCent
Martin Weiss	New York Hall of Science

September 6-10, 2006

**Fossil & Molecular Estimates of Divergence Times for the
Tree of Life
Working Group
Coordinator: Todd Oakley**

Participants:

Charles Bell	Xavier University
Debashish Bhattacharya	University of Iowa
Tom Britton	University of Stockholm
Julia Clarke	North Carolina State University
Lee-Hsiang Liow	University of Chicago
Susana Magallon	Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México
Dan McShea	Duke University
Johannes Muller	University of Toronto
Nathalie Nagalingum	Duke University
Thomas Near	University of Tennessee, Yale University
Michael Nowak	Duke University
Todd Oakley	University of California - Santa Barbara
Kevin Peterson	Dartmouth College
Susannah Porter	University of California - Santa Barbara
Fredrik Ronquist	Florida State University
Jeff Thorne	North Carolina State University
Peter Wagner	The Field Museum
Brian Wiegmann	North Carolina State University
Greg Wray	Duke University
Anne Yoder	Duke University

September 17 – 20, 2006

**The Plant EvoGenetics: Advancing Comparative
Functional Genomics
Working Group
Coordinators: Jim Leebens-Mack
Eric Brenner**

Participants:

John Bowers	University of Georgia
Eric Brenner	New York Botanic Gardens
Steve Cannon	Iowa State University
Claude dePamphilis	Pennsylvania State University
Mary Egan Montclair	State University
Stefanie Hartmann	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Jim Leebens-Mack	University of Georgia
David Liberles	University of Wyoming
Bill Piel	University of Arizona
Shin-Han Shiu	Michigan State University
Kimmen Sjolander	University of California - Berkeley
Dennis Stevenson	New York Botanic Gardens
Val Tannen	University of Pennsylvania
Todd Vision	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill

Kerr Wall
Tandy Warnow
Rob DeSalle

Pennsylvania State University
University of Texas
American Museum of Natural History

November 12 – 14, 2006

**Towards an Integrated Database for Fish Evolution
Working Group
Coordinators: Paula Mabee
Monte Westerfield**

Participants:

Gloria Arratia
Miles Coburn
Mark Gibson
Melissa Haendel
Eric Hilton
John Lundberg
Paula Mabee
Rick Mayden
Chris Mungall
Gavin Naylor
Nelson Rios
Monte Westerfield

University of Kansas
John Carroll University
Berkeley Livermore Laboratory
University of Oregon
Field Museum of Natural History
Academy of Natural Sciences
University of South Dakota
St. Louis University
Howard Hughes Medical Institute
Florida State University
Tulane University
University of Oregon

Informatics Meeting

January 18, 2006

**GMOD Informatics Advisory Meeting
Coordinators: Cliff Cunningham
Todd Vision**

Participants:

Scott Cain
Terry Casstevens
Quentin Cronk
Cliff Cunningham
David Emmert
Owen McMillan
Tom Mitchell-Olds
Chris Mungall
Nassib Nassar
Mohammed Noor
Robert Reed
Jason Stajich
Lincoln Stein
Todd Vision
John Willis
Greg Wray

Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
Cornell University
University of British Columbia and NESCent
Duke University and NESCent
Harvard University
University of Puerto Rico and NESCent
Duke University
University of California - Berkeley
NESCent
Duke University
Duke University
Duke University
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill and NESCent
Duke University
Duke University

Education Meetings

April 20 – 21, 2006

Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities Advisory Meeting

Coordinators: Greg Gibson

Kristin Jenkins

Jory Weintraub

Participants:

Margaret Connors
Christian d'Orgeix
Joe Fail
Greg Gibson
Joseph Graves
Kristin Jenkins
Bonnie Kelley
Lee Anne Martinez
Camellia Okpodu
Abe Parker
Kathleen Smith
Geri Twitty
Jory Weintraub

NCEAS
Virginia State University
Johnson C. Smith University
NESCent
North Carolina A&T State University
NESCent
University of North Carolina - Pembroke
Colorado State University - Pueblo
Norfolk State University
AIBS
NESCent
Howard University
NESCent

July 10-12, 2006

Evolution Education Working Group

Coordinators: Greg Gibson

Kristin Jenkins

Jory Weintraub

Participants:

Brian Alters
Alan Berkowitz
Rodger Bybee
Judy Diamond
Sam Donovan
Margaret Evans
Kristen Fisher
Douglas Futuyma
Yolanda George
Greg Gibson
Kristin Jenkins
John Jungck
Jay Labov
Dennis Liu
Susan Musante
Craig Nelson
Richard O'Grady
Rob Pennock
Jenn Piascik

Evolution Education Research Centre, McGill University
Institute of Ecosystem Studies
Biological Sciences Curriculum Study
University of Nebraska State Museum
University of Pittsburgh
University of Michigan
NESCent
State University of New York - Stony Brook
American Association for the Advancement of Science
NESCent
NESCent
Beloit College and BioQUEST
National Academies
Howard Hughes Medical Institute
American Institute of Biological Sciences
Indiana University
American Institute of Biological Sciences
Michigan State University
North Carolina State University

Sam Price	NESCent
Malcolm Schug	University of North Carolina - Greensboro
Judy Scotchmoor	University of California Museum of Paleontology
Eugenie Scott	National Center for Science Education
Kathleen Smith	NESCent
Mark Terry	The Northwest School
Gordon Uno	University of Oklahoma
Jory Weintraub	NESCent
Martin Weiss	New York Hall of Science

Appendix A.6.

Participant Lists - Other Supported Activities December 1, 2005 – November 30, 2006

Workshop Co-Sponsored by NESCent

January 31 – February 3, 2006

Global Unique Identifiers Workshop (GUID-1)

Location: NESCent

**Coordinator: Ricardo Pereira
(NESCent contributed \$5,000)**

Participants:

Lee Belbin	International Working Group on Taxonomic Databases (TDWG)
Stan Blum	California Academy of Sciences
Simon Coppard	International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN)
Peter Dawyndt	The World Federation for Culture Collections (WFCC)
Dag Terje Endersen	International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI)
Scott Federhen	GenBank
George Garrity	Bergey's Manual Trust - Michigan State University
Gerald Guala	United States Department of Agriculture (USDA)
Bryan Heidorn	University of Illinois
Sally Hinchcliffe	International Plant Names Index (IPNI)
Donald Hobern	Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)
Robert Huber	MARUM - Institute for Marine Environmental Sciences
Roger Hyam	International Working Group on Taxonomic Databases (TDWG)
Andrew Jones	Catalogue of Life
Matt Jones	National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS)
Jessie Kennedy	Napier University
Paul Kirk	CABI Bioscience
Roderic Page	University of Glasgow
Bob Peet	University of North Carolina
Ricardo Pereira	International Working Group on Taxonomic Databases (TDWG)
Richard Pyle	Bishop Museum
Kevin Richards	Landcare Research
Rodney Spears	University of Kansas
Hideaki Sugawara	DNA Data Bank of Japan
Benjamin Szekely	IBM
Kevin Thiele	Centre for Biological Information Technology (CBIT)
Mark Wilkinson	
M. I. Zuberi	University of Rajshahi

Conference Reception Hosted by NESCent from Provost Discretionary Funds

March 10, 2006

A Tree of Life Conference Reception

Location: NESCent
Coordinators: Shannon Hackett
Cliff Cunningham

Participants:

Jonathan Armbruster	Blair Hedges
Gloria Arratia	John Heraty
James Baldwin	David Hillis
Bernie Ball	Julian Humphries
Henry Bart	Zachary Ives
Reed Beaman	Jason Jackson
Jonathan Bennet	Tim James
Debashish Bhattacharya	Robert Jansen
Lynn Bohs	Gera Jochum
Sandy Boles	Gail Kampmeier
Greg Bonito	Laura Katz
Jeffrey Boore	Frank Kauff
Se-n Brady	Seth Kaufman
Edward Braun	Junhyong Kim
Mike Braun	Rebecca Kimball
David Cannatella	Carlos Lado
Paulyn Cartwright	Louise Lewis
Mark Clement	Paul Lewis
Miles Coburn	Randy Linder
Allen Collins	John Logsdon
Greg Courtney	John Lundberg
Keith Crandall	FranÁois Lutzoni
Barbara Crandall-Stotler	Charles Lydeard
Quentin Cronk	David Maddison
Michael Cummings	Joel Martin
Cliff Cunningham	Steve Mayden
Christine Davis	Richard McCourt
Chuck Davis	Catherine McFadden
Paul De Ley	Kathleen Miglia
Michael Donoghue	Mark Miller
Norman Douglas	Dan Miranker
Brian Farrell	Brent Mishler
Daphne Fautin	Charles Mitter
Darryl Felder	William Moore
Rodney Feldmann	Juan Carlos Morales
David Gaitros	Bernard Moret
Gonzalo Giribet	Steve Nadler
Bernard Goffinet	Nathalie Nagalingum
Shannon Hackett	Maureen O'Leary
Ken Halanych	Gisela Oliv-n
Nikki Hanegan	Larry Page
James Hanken	Jeri Parrent
Phillip Harris	David Patterson
John Harshman	Diana Percy

Kathryn Perez
Bill Piel
Lisa Pokorny
Yin-Long Qiu
Tod Reeder
Jerry Regier
Steve Rehner
Hannah Reynolds
Nelson Rios
Frederick Ronquist
Tim Rowe
Mark Sabaj
Mary Beth Saffo
Randall Schuh
Ted Schultz
Carrie Schweitzer
Paul Sereno
Michael Sharkey
Blanka Shaw
Jon Shaw
Petra Sierwald
Cynthia Sims Parr

Judith Skog
Joey Spatafora
Frederick Spiegel
David Spooner
Steve Stephenson
Ray Stotler
David Swofford
Carl Taylor
Kelley Thomas
Jeff Thorne
Rytas Vilgalys
Todd Vision
David Wake
Marvalee Wake
Tandy Warnow
Susan Weller
Michael Whiting
Brian Wiegmann
Robert Wood
David Yeates
Ping Zhou
Derrick Zwickl

Workshop Co-Sponsored by NESCent with Provost Discretionary Funds

May 8-9, 2006

Recovering DNA from Formalin Fixed Biological Samples

Location: Washington, D.C.

Coordinator: David Schindel

The Board on Life Sciences convened a two-day advanced research workshop to discuss the future of DNA recovery from formalin-preserved biological specimens. The workshop brought together chemists, biophysicists, biochemists, geneticists, and bioinformaticians to examine past attempts on DNA recovery from formalin-preserved biological specimens and discussed the research needed to advance the development of similar but more efficient and cost-effective protocols. The goal of the workshop was the development of a research agenda that would shed new light on the problem and lead to a solution.

Course Co-Supported by NESCent with Provost Discretionary Funds

July 2006

Paleobiology Database Summer Course

Location: Santa Barbara, CA

Coordinator: John Alroy

This Paleobiology Database summer course was co-sponsored with NCEAS and the Paleontological Society. Topics included divergence time estimation, tree imbalance, phylogeny-based biogeographic methods and the relationships of higher-order groups. The

course was dominated by such evolutionary topics as morphometrics, processes of speciation and extinction, and phylogenetic.

Triangle Working Group Meetings Funded with Provost Discretionary Funds

May 18, 2006

**Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular
Biology and Paleontology
North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences, Raleigh
Coordinators: Julia Clarke
Nathalie Nagalingum
Brian Weigmann**

Participants:

Matt Bertone	North Carolina State University
Art Bogan	North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences
Robert Brandon	Duke University
Steve Busack	North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences
Sang-Chul Choi	North Carolina State University
Julia Clarke	North Carolina State University
Mia Feng	North Carolina State University
Pat Gensel	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
A. J. Harris	North Carolina State University
David Hearn	Duke University
Paul Manos	Duke University
Nathalie Nagalingum	Duke University
Mike Nowak	Duke University
Sam Price	NESCent
Kathleen Pryer	Duke University
Alex Rosenberg	Duke University
Mary Schweitzer	North Carolina State University
Adam Smith	North Carolina State University
Wayne Starnes	North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences
Jeff Thorne	North Carolina State University
Michelle Trautwein	North Carolina State University
Brian Wiegmann	North Carolina State University
Jenny Xiang	North Carolina State University
Anne Yoder	Duke University
Wenheng Zhang	North Carolina State University

November 17, 2006

**Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular
Biology and Paleontology
NESCent
Coordinators: Julia Clarke
Nathalie Nagalingum
Brian Weigmann**

Participants:

Matt Bertone	North Carolina State University
Robert Brandon	Duke University
Sang-Chul Choi	North Carolina State University
Julia Clarke	North Carolina State University
Mia Feng	North Carolina State University
Pat Gensel	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
A. J. Harris	North Carolina State University
David Hearn	Duke University
Paul Manos	Duke University
Nathalie Nagalingum	Duke University
Mike Nowak	Duke University
Sam Price	NESCent
Kathleen Pryer	Duke University
Alex Rosenberg	Duke University
Mary Schweitzer	North Carolina State University
Adam Smith	North Carolina State University
Jeff Thorne	North Carolina State University
Michelle Trautwein	North Carolina State University
Brian Wiegmann	North Carolina State University
Jenny Xiang	North Carolina State University
Anne Yoder	Duke University
Wenheng Zhang	North Carolina State University

Appendix A.7.

Other Meetings Held at NESCent - Not Funded by NESCent

December 1, 2005 – November 30, 2006

January 28-31, 2006

SEEK Meeting
Coordinator: Bob Peet

Participants:

James Beach	University of Kansas
Laura Downey	LTER, University of New Mexico
Robert Gales	University of Kansas
Susan Gauch	University of Kansas
Patricia Gensel	NESCent and University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Martin Graham	Napier University
Matt Jones	NCEAS
Jessie Kennedy	Napier University
Xianhua Liu	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Bob Peet	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Milo Pyne	NatureServe, SE Regional Office
Aimee Stewart	University of Kansas
Todd Vision	NESCent and University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Alan Weakley	NESCent and University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Thomas Wentworth	North Carolina State University

March 3, 2006

**Computational Approaches and Mathematical Models
for Genetic Polymorphisms in the Function of Folate
Metabolism and DNA Methylation**
Coordinator: Fred Nijhout

Participants:

Alanna Boynton	Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center
Jess Gregory	University of Florida
Marian Neuhauser	Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center
Fred Nijhout	Duke University
Mike Reed	Duke University
Barry Shane	University of California - Berkeley
Neli Ulrich	Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center

March 9, 2006

**A Tree of Life Conference (pre-meeting)
Coordinator: Shannon Hackett**

Participants:

Ed Braun	University of Florida
Michael Braun	Smithsonian
Shannon Hackett	Field Museum
Kin-Lan Han	Smithsonian
John Harshman	Field Museum
Chris Huddleston	Smithsonian
Rebecca Kimball	University of Florida
Ben Marks	Louisiana State University
Kathy Miglia	Wayne State University
William Moore	Wayne State University
Sushma Reddy	Field Museum
Tamaki Yuri	Smithsonian

June 14, 2006

**Phylogenetic Analysis with Complex Genome
Rearrangement Events Meeting
Coordinator: Jijun Tang**

Participants:

Eva Czabarka	University of South Carolina
Yan Guo	University of South Carolina
James David Henson	University of South Carolina
Kirk McMullan	University of South Carolina
Laslow Szekely	University of South Carolina
Jijun Tang	University of South Carolina
Todd Vision	NESCent

June 29 – 30, 2006

**GMOD Developers Meeting
Coordinator: Scott Cain**

Participants:

Sam Angiuoli	TIGR
Scott Cain	GMOD
Terry Casstevens	Gramene
Malcolm Cook	Stowers Institute for Medical Research
Jonathan Crabtree	TIGR
Stan Dong	SGD
David Emmert	FlyBase
Ben Faga	GMOD

Don Gilbert	Indiana University
Arek Kasprzyk	EBI/CSHL
David Kidd	NESCent
Hilmar Lapp	NESCent
Suzanna Lewis	BDGP
Sheldon McKay	WormBase
Owen McMillan	NESCent
Paul Mooney	Sanger Institute
Brian O'Connor	UCLA
Joshua Orvis	TIGR
Suzanne Paley	EcoCyc
Helen Pan	RTI International
Xiaokang Pan	SynBrowse
Joel Richardson	MGI
Sofia Robb	PlanariaDB
Eric Ross	PlanariaDB
Jason Stajich	Duke University
Lincoln Stein	WormBase
Todd Vision	NESCent
John Willis	Duke University
Henry Xiang	Novozymes, Inc.
Fengkai (Tony) Zhang	Virginia Bioinformatics Institute
Peili Zhang	FlyBase
Pinglei Zhou	FlyBase

August 23-26, 2006

**Developing and Integrating Taxonomic Databases for the
21st Century**

Coordinator: Patricia Gensel

Participants:

John Alroy	NCEAS/PBDB
Reed Beaman	Yale University
Michael Benton	University of Bristol, UK
Stanley Blum	California Academy of Sciences
Ann Budd	University of Iowa
Marc Carrasco	University of California - Berkeley
Joseph Carter	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Cinzia Cervato	Iowa State University
Kerin Claesen	University of Texas - Austin
Edward Davis	University of California - Berkeley
Vladimir Davydov	Boise State University
Patrick Diver	CHRONOS
Jean Dougherty	Geological Survey of Canada
Pat Gensel	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Jill Hardesty	University of Kansas
Pat Herendeen	National Science Foundation
Brian Huber	USNM
Thomas Kammer	West Virginia University

Jessie Kennedy	Napier University, UK
David Lazarus	Berlin Museum Natural History
Scott Lidgard	The Field Museum
Josh Madin	NCEAS
Peter McCartney	National Science Foundation
Charles Mitchell	University at Buffalo
Lisa Parks	University of Akron
Robert Peet	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Hermann Pfefferkorn	University of Pennsylvania
David Remsen	GBIF, ubio
Judy Skog	National Science Foundation
Walt Snyder	Boise State University
Jessica Theodor	University of Calgary
Mark Uhen	Cranbrook Institute of Science
Peter Wagner	University of Chicago
Tim White	Yale University

Appendix A.8.

NESCent Senior Advisory Board and Science Review Board Members

Senior Advisory Board Members

- Dr. Scott V. Edwards**, Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Harvard University
- Dr. David Hillis**, Section of Integrative Biology, University of Texas, Austin
- Dr. David Jablonski**, Department of Geophysical Sciences, University of Chicago
- Dr. Elizabeth A. Kellogg**, Department of Biology, University of Missouri – St. Louis
- Dr. Emilia P. Martins**, Department of Biology, Indiana University
- Dr. Lisa M. Nagy**, Department of Molecular and Cellular Biology, University of Arizona
- Dr. James Reichman**, Ecology, Evolution and Marine Biology, University of California, Santa Barbara; NCEAS
- Dr. Barbara Schaal**, Department of Biology, Washington University at St. Louis
- Dr. Simon Tavaré**, Molecular and Computational Biology, University of Southern California

Resignation Effective April 2006:

Dr. Emilia P. Martins

Science Review Board Members

Original Members:

- Dr. Lisa Donovan**, Department of Plant Biology, University of Georgia
- Dr. Jonathan A. Eisen**, Department of Microbial Genomics, The Institute for Genomic Research
- Dr. Fred L. Gould**, Department of Entomology, North Carolina State University
- Dr. Elizabeth A. Hadly**, Department of Biological Sciences, Stanford University
- Dr. Laura A. Katz**, Department of Biological Sciences, Smith College
- Dr. Thomas Kaufman**, Department of Biology, Indiana University
- Dr. Joel Kingsolver**, Department of Biology, University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
- Dr. Hirohisa Kishino**, Laboratory of Biometry & Bioinformatics, University of Tokyo
- Dr. Jonathan B. Losos**, Department of Biology, Washington University in St. Louis
- Dr. Sarah P. Otto**, Department of Zoology, University of British Columbia
- Dr. Paul Turner**, Dept. of Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, Yale University
- Dr. Sara Via**, Department of Biology & Entomology, University of Maryland
- Dr. Peter Wainwright**, Division of Biological Science, University of California, Davis
- Dr. Katherine Willis**, School of Geography & Environment, University of Oxford
- Dr. Marlene Zuk**, Department of Biology, University of California, Riverside

Members Added September 2005:

Dr. Catherine Graham, Department of Ecology & Evolution, SUNY at Stony Brook

Dr. Junhyong Kim, Department of Biology, University of Pennsylvania

Dr. Joseph E. Neigel, Department of Biology, University of Louisiana at Lafayette

Dr. Peter Wagner, Department of Geology, The Field Museum, Chicago

Members Added December 2006:

Dr. Stan Blum, California Academy of Sciences

Dr. Troy Day, Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Queens University

Dr. William Piel, Peabody Museum of Natural History, Yale University

Dr. Hopi Hoekstra, Department of Biology, University of California, San Diego

Dr. Todd Strelman, Department of Biology, Georgia Tech University

Dr. Bruce Rannala, Section of Evolutionary and Ecology, University of California, Davis

Member Added June 2007:

Dr. Tony Zera, School of Biological Sciences, University of Nebraska

Resignations Effective December 2006:

Dr. Thomas Kaufman

Dr. Sara Via

Appendix A.9.

Products by NESCent Scientists – Years 1 & 2 Publications, Presentations, Software/Databases, and Websites Through October 2006

I. POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWS

Publications

Kidd, D. M., and M. G. Ritchie. 2006. Phylogeographic information systems; Putting the geography into phylogeography. *Journal of Biogeography* 33:1851-1865.

Pepin and **Kidd** (in press). Temperatures in the Eastern Pyrenees. *Weather*.

Presentations

David Kidd: The Influence of Landscape and Climate on the Evolution of Biodiversity in the European Bushcricket Genus *Ephippiger*, *Duke University Biology Systematics Seminar*, 2.23.06.

David Kidd: The role of climate and landscape in structuring biodiversity in the genus *Ephippiger*. *NESCent Session, Evolution 2006, Stony Brook*, 6.26.06.

David Kidd: And Then There Were Two: Revealing Patterns of Spatiotemporal Bifurcation with GIS & CART. *GISRUK 2006, Nottingham UK*, 4.6.06.

David Kidd: Visualizing Phylogeographic Pattern. *GMOD meeting NESCent*, 6.30.06.

David Kidd: Pleistocene climate change drives phylogenetic niche diversification and convergence in the European bushcricket genus *Ephippiger*? *UNC Chapel Hill Biology Seminar*, 9.2.06.

David Kidd: Paraclimatic Niche Diversification in the Genus *Ephippiger*. *Paleogeography and Palaeobiogeography: Biodiversity in Space and Time*. National Institute for Environmental eScience, Cambridge, UK. 4.10-13 2006. (poster)

Samantha Price: Extrapolating from extant to extinct: reconstruction of neocete life history strategy and ecology' Symposium at SVP meeting October 2006.

Software and Databases

James Balhoff: Wrote a user-friendly interface for GARLI, a phylogenetic inference program created by fellow post-doc **Derrick Zwickl**. Continuing to enhance my version of GARLI as Zwickl adds features.

Josh Granek: Development of a software tool, GOMER, for identifying conserved regulatory function. GOMER predicts the probability that a regulatory sequence will be bound by a transcription factor, by integrating over all the potential binding sites within the sequence

David Kidd: PhyloBuilder v1.0 for ArcGIS 9.0 to be release September/October 2006. Supports: Creation of spatiotemporal phylogeny from NEWICK tree and associated files defining sample locations. Sample locations can be points (e.g. individuals), lines (e.g. river reaches) or polygons (e.g. population). Tree depths are assigned to network nodes allowing 3D visualization in ArcScene.

Samantha Price: Cetacean Biology Database - Improved database on cetacean life history traits with new traits added: diet, swimming speeds, dive depths. This is ongoing but should be completed by April 2007.

Derrick Zwickl: Updated and released my phylogenetic inference software GARLI. Available at <http://www.zo.utexas.edu/faculty/antisense/garli/Garli.html>.

Grants and Grant Proposals:

David Kidd: NESCent Working Group: Phylogeographic Pattern, Speciation, and Niche Projections into the Late Pleistocene. Co-PI with Town Peterson, Natural History Museum & Biodiversity Research Center and Department of Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, The University of Kansas.

New Collaborations:

James Balhoff: With sabbatarian **Quentin Cronk** developing a data editor for phenotypic data matrices. Quentin is leading efforts to incorporate the use of ontology terms (controlled scientific vocabulary) into phenotypic descriptions in order to improve the "computability" of such datasets. Without the use of ontology terms, free-text descriptions of phenotypic traits are very difficult to combine across datasets and are of little use to automated software tools. I am developing an application which allows users to create a character list using the Entity, Attribute, Value scheme for phenotypic descriptions, which represents characters using ontology terms. Creating an easy-to-use application for composing these datasets may accelerate the rate at which ontologies are adopted in evolutionary biology.”

Samantha Price: Predicting zoonotic outbreaks from bushmeat consumption with Dr. Amy Pedersen. This uses the mammal parasite data, existing global databases of human disease and my previous work on bushmeat and hunting.

Samantha Price: Aquatic mammal parasites with Independent study student. This is an addition to the terrestrial mammal parasite database. It is particularly pertinent, as recent research has shown an increase incidence of disease in marine environments.

Samantha Price: Evolution of horns in Bovids with Dr. Vincent Savolainen and Dr. Jonathan Davies. This uses the artiodactyl habitat data and my phylogeny from my PhD along with the horn length data collected by my colleagues.

II. SABBATICAL SCHOLARS

Publications:

Clamp, J. Phylogeny of *Zoothamnium*. Journal of Eukaryotic Microbiology, in press.

Citerne HL, Pennington RT, **Cronk QC**. An apparent reversal in floral symmetry in the legume *Cadia* is a homeotic transformation. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 2006 Aug 8;103(32):12017-20. Epub 2006 Jul 31.

Gilchrist EJ, Haughn GW, Ying CC, Otto SP, Zhuang J, Cheung D, Hamberger B, Aboutorabi F, Kalynyak T, Johnson L, Bohlmann J, Ellis BE, Douglas CJ, **Cronk QC**. Use of Ecotilling as an efficient SNP discovery tool to survey genetic variation in wild populations of *Populus trichocarpa*. Mol Ecol. 2006 Apr;15(5):1367-78.

Cronk QC. Legume flowers bear fruit. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 2006 Mar 28;103(13):4801-2. Epub 2006 Mar 27. No abstract available.

Cronk Q, Ojeda I, Pennington RT. Legume comparative genomics: progress in phylogenetics and phylogenomics. Curr Opin Plant Biol. 2006 Apr;9(2):99-103. Epub 2006 Feb 15. Review.

Cronk, Q. 329 page synthesis manuscript, *The Molecular Organography of Plants*, written while at NESCENT (to be published by Oxford University Press).

Tuskan G, **Cronk Q**, et al. The genome of black cottonwood, *Populus trichocarpa* (Torr. & Gray ex Brayshaw). Science, in press.

Eyre-Walker, A., Woolfit, M. & Phelps, T. The distribution of fitness effects of new deleterious amino acid mutations in humans. Genetics 173, 891-900 (2006).

Charlesworth, J. & **Eyre-Walker, A.** The rate of adaptive evolution in enteric bacteria. Mol. Biol. Evol. in press (2006).

Eyre-Walker, A. The genomic rate of adaptive evolution. Trends Ecol Evol (2006).

Eyre-Walker, A. Evolution. Size does not matter for mitochondrial DNA. *Science* 312, 537-8 (2006).

D. W. Foltz, M. T. Bolton, S. P. Kelley, B. D. Kelley and A. T. Nguyen [in press] Combined mitochondrial and nuclear sequences support the monophyly of forcipulatacean sea stars. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, online <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2006.10.012>.

Presentations:

Quentin Cronk: UNC Biology Department, Seminar, 15 November 2005, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill

Quentin Cronk: NCSU, Statistical Genetics Department seminar program, 25 January 2006

Adam Eyre-Walker: Society of Molecular Biology Conference – Phoenix, AZ

Adam Eyre-Walker: International Society of Molecular Evolution – Ischia, Italy

Adam Eyre-Walker: Marine Genomics Meeting – Banyuls-Sur-Mer, France

Adam Eyre-Walker: UNC Chapel Hill – Chapel Hill, NC

Adam Eyre-Walker: NC State – Raleigh, NC

Adam Eyre-Walker: Rutgers University – Piscataway, NJ

Adam Eyre-Walker: Cedar Crest College – Allentown, PA

Adam Eyre-Walker: University of Texas – Austin, TX

Adam Eyre-Walker: Georgia Tech – Atlanta, GA

Lewis, P. O., and Yu Fan. A posterior predictive loss approach to model selection in Bayesian phylogenetics. Poster presented at the CIPRES annual meeting in Austin, Texas, 2-4 February, 2006.

Lewis, P. O. Model selection in the Bayesian era. Colloquium, Systematics Seminar Series, Department of Biology, Duke University, April 6, 2006.

Lewis, P. O. Phylogenetics in the Bayesian era. Colloquium, Institute of Statistics and Decision Sciences, Duke University, April 14, 2006.

Lewis, P. O., and Yu Fan. “A minimum posterior predictive loss approach to Bayesian phylogenetic model selection. SSE meetings SUNY Stony brook, 2006:

Lewis, P. O., and Derrick Zwickl. Using Bayesian rjMCMC to infer the number of categories in a general discrete distribution approach to among-site rate heterogeneity. SSE meetings SUNY Stony brook, 2006 (NESCent Mini-symposium)

Software and Databases:

John Clamp: Databases containing information about programs at MSIs and other institutions with significant minority enrollment and institutions with graduate programs in evolutionary biology. Available at:

John Clamp: A network for electronic exchange of information between minority institutions and research institutions with evolutionary biology graduate programs. This includes distribution lists for e-mail messages and a set of web pages on the EOG portion of the NESCent site for access to information.

Adam Eyre-Walker: I have developed two computer programs which will be freely available to the public. *DoFE* a program which implements various methods to estimate components of the distribution of fitness effects, including the method developed at Nescent. I also have a program which calculates Tajima's Q."

Paul Lewis: PHYCAS is being written collaboratively by myself, Mark T. Holder and David L. Swofford. PHYCAS represents both a C++/Python library as well as an end-user application. CIPRES will benefit most from the library aspect of PHYCAS, whereas the PHYCAS application will perform standalone Bayesian and maximum likelihood analyses and be useful to end users who are not interested in downloading/installing the entire CIPRES software suite. The current phase of CIPRES involves replacing legacy applications with code specifically written for the CIPRES platform. PHYCAS will serve that purpose, providing functionality now being provided by PAUP*, MrBayes, and several other programs.... While I made considerable progress on PHYCAS this semester, it is still not developed to the point where it can be released. NESCent hosted a PHYCAS developers working session 17-21 May, 2006. At this working session, we (i.e. Mark Holder, David Swofford and I) concentrated on speeding up the likelihood calculations in PHYCAS and implementing "underflow" protection to allow analysis of large datasets. These were two of the biggest obstacles to releasing PHYCAS, so I am now hopeful that a first (beta) release of the PHYCAS application will be possible before the end of summer 2006.

Owen McMillan: We have now finished our initial evolutionary extensions to Chado. The new schema is about 90% "Chadoized" and about 90% complete. The project is currently posted on sourceforge (<http://sourceforge.net/projects/heliconiusdb/>), and includes the base GMOD schema (chado.psql), our evolutionary extensions (evo.psql), some default data (base_data.psql) and much of my *Heliconius* data (mcmillan.psql).

Grants and Grant Proposal:

Todd Vision: I helped to co-organize a NESCent-GMOD meeting in January with Owen McMillan. This served as the seed for NESCent's current partnership with GMOD, which resulted in a 2006 proposal to the NIH to provide support for a GMOD helpdesk and development of software of use for evolutionary model organisms. GMOD also held their annual developers meeting at NESCent, at which the genome software development

community was apprised of some of the informatics issues of importance to the evolutionary model organism community.

New Collaboration:

John Clamp: I was invited to spend the month of April, 2006 in the laboratory of Prof. Dr. Weibo Song, Ocean University of China, Xingdao, P.R. China. While there, I established collaborations with several individuals in Dr. Song's lab. I have also made a collaborative agreement with Dr. Wei Miao of the Chinese Academy of Sciences, Wuhan, P.R.C. Both of these collaborations will extend indefinitely and have the potential to generate appreciable international exchange between my department and my Chinese collaborators. I hope to obtain funding to return to China on a regular basis and to take minority students with me.

III. WORKING GROUPS AND CATALYSIS MEETINGS

Publications:

Moore, B. A. and M. J. Donoghue. 2007. Correlates of diversification in the plant clade Dipsacales: geographic movement versus evolutionary innovation. *Am. Nat.* (in review).

Grimm, G., S. S. Renner, A. Stamatakis, and V. Hemleben. 2006 (due to appear Oct or Nov). A nuclear ribosomal DNA phylogeny of *Acer* inferred with maximum likelihood, splits graphs, and motif analyses of 606 sequences. *Evolutionary Bioinformatics*.

Renner, S. S., L. Beenken, G. W. Grimm, A. Kocyan, and R. E. Ricklefs. Sexual system evolution in *Acer*: Plasticity in resource allocation versus dioecy. (Submitted to *Evolution*)

Penney, D. (in press) Hispaniolan spider biodiversity and the importance of combining neontological and palaeontological data in analyses of historical biogeography. In: *Focus on Biodiversity Research*. Nova Science Publishers Inc., New York. Invited submission.

Penney, D. (in review) Continental affinities of Hispaniolan spiders provide support for GAARlandia landspan. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*

Kelly, J. K. 2006. An approximation to mutation-selection balance in a mixed mating population. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, in review.

Mabee, P. M., G. Arratia, M. Coburn, M. Haendel, E. J. Hilton, J. G. Lundberg, R. L. Mayden, N. Rios, M. Westerfield. Connecting evolutionary morphology to genomics using ontologies: A case study from Cypriniformes including zebrafish. Submitted (Sept 06).

Mabee, P.M., M. Ashburner, Q. Cronk, G. V. Gkoutos, M. Haendel, C. Mungall, E. Segerdell, M. Westerfield. Phenotype ontologies make the link between genomics and evolution. In revision (May 2006).

Presentations:

P. Mabee, A. Worthington, E. Grey. July 2006 “*Relating evolutionary and model organism phenotypes using ontologies*”. Poster presentation (American Society of Ichthyology and Herpetology)

P. Mabee. May 2006. Attended and participated in the workshop “*Ontology and Phylogeny*” in St. Louis (organized by M. Oliver and B. Mishler through NSF Deep Gene RCN). May 21-24, 2006.

P. Mabee. Feb. 2006. Presented an invited talk at the AAAS meeting entitled “*Anatomy, Morphology, and Ontogeny Spanning the Tree of Life*” in the symposium “Assembling the Tree of Life: Today and in the Future”. Feb. 18-20, 2006.

P. Mabee. Jan. 2006. Presented an invited talk in the Zebrafish Symposium at the SICB meeting: “*Integrating CToL-related studies with available phenotype & genomics databases for the zebrafish*”. Co-authors: M. Westerfield, M. Haendel, G. Arratia, M. Coburn, E. Hilton, J. Lundberg, C. Lushbough, R. Mayden, N. Rios Society of Integrative and Comparative Biology meetings (Tampa, FL, January 4-8, 2006) *Our work, as presented in this talk, was commented on in Science (Pennisi 2006) Pennisi E. 2006. Fishing for common ground. Science 311: 766-767.

P. Mabee. Dec. 2005. Presented a poster of NESCent working groups’ activities at the First International Biocurator’s meeting (Asilomar, CA, Dec. 8-11, 2005). Co-authors on the poster were other members of our working group: M. Westerfield, M. Haendel, G. Arratia, M. Coburn, E. Hilton, J. Lundberg, C. Lushbough, R. Mayden, and N. Rios. “*Relating evolutionary and model organism phenotypes using ontologies*”.

Donoghue, M.J., and B.R. Moore. 2006. Correlates of diversification in the plant clade Dipsacales: Geographic movement versus evolutionary innovation. Evolution Meeting (Stonybrook, NY). *Invited presentation in the ASN Vice Presidential Symposium “Merging ecological and evolutionary approaches to understanding geographic gradients in species richness”, organized by Susan Harrison and Michael Bell.

Moore, B.R., Q.-Y. Xiang, J. Thorne, D. Thomas, and M.J. Donoghue. 2006. Biogeographic and biological correlates of diversification in dogwoods: Dispersal and evolution of fruits and inflorescences in space and time. Evolution Meeting (Stonybrook, NY).

Ree, R.H., B.R. Moore, S.A. Smith, and M.J. Donoghue. 2006. A likelihood framework for inferring biogeographic history. Evolution Meeting (Stonybrook, NY).

Ree, R.H., B.R. Moore, S.A. Smith, and M.J. Donoghue. 2005. Likelihood-based inference of historical biogeography. Missouri Botanical Gardens Meeting (St. Louis, MO). *Invited

presentation in the symposium "Reconstructing complex evolutionary histories: Gene-species trees, historical biogeography, and coevolution", organized by Richard Mayden.

Fritsch, P. W., F. Almeda, and S. R. Manchester. 2006. Phylogeny and classification of Symplocaceae: stasis, ranks, and the fossil record. ASPT annual meeting, Chico, CA.

Donoghue, M.J. Testing models of historical biogeography: insights from the flowering plant families Styrcaceae and Symplocaceae. Hunan Normal University, China. September 12, 2006.

Grants and Grant Proposals:

Donoghue, M.J. "Collaborative Research: Phylogenetics and biogeographic studies of the Citroideae and Rutaceae", National Science Foundation DEB-Systematic Biology, 3 years, \$66,227. With Cynthia Morton, Carnegie Museum of Natural History. Submitted 10 July 2006.

Donoghue, M.J. "Collaborative Research: Phylogenetic, biogeographic, and monographic studies in the wintergreen group (Gaultherieae, Ericaceae)", National Science Foundation, \$254,287. With Kathleen Kron, Wake Forest University, and Walter Judd, University of Florida. (Re-)submitted, 18 July 2006.

Mabee, P. M. (PI), Vision, T. (co-PI), Westerfield, M. (co-PI). PENDING (Submitted 10 July 2006): Linking evolution to genomics using phenotype ontologies. \$1,769,501; 1 June 2007-31 May 2010. NSF Biological Databases and Informatics.

New Collaborations:

Glor and Perkins are currently preparing a collaborative grant proposal that will combine biogeographic analyses of lizards and their malarial parasites. This grant will be submitted to the National Science Foundation in the Winter of 2007.

Losos, Ricklefs, Knouft, and Jon Chase will prepare proposal in 2007 to compare the assembly of colonization-based (birds) and diversification-based (lizards) island biotas.

NESCENT-sponsored Morphobank-MorphBank collaboration:

Database:

"We adjusted the MorphoBank data model to encourage interoperability between the Florida project and our systems. Specifically, we added structures that existed in Morphobank but were not previously in MORPHOBANK. These structures underlie features and concepts that were not of primary concern to MORPHOBANK, but were not incompatible with our mission. We felt that the increased complexity these features brought to our system was more than offset by the common vocabulary their inclusion made possible. These structures included "views," and aspects relating to taxonomy and specimens.

Web application:

“As noted above, we completed the MORPHOBANK online matrix editor with the support of NESCent. This is a phylogenetic data editor (akin to MacClade or Mesquite) that is a fully operational web application already under use by practicing systematists. That means that authors can upload and download Nexus files, media (including 2D images, CT scans, etc...) and taxonomic information. These images can be affiliated with taxonomies and with cells in a matrix to demonstrate morphological homology statements. This is a very effective tool for collaborators who are not in the same geographical area but who need to share data. It has the potential to be particularly effective for collaborations between scientists in the USA and poorer countries where there is less scientific infrastructure. MORPHOBANK is both a platform for collaboration and an archive. Data remain private and password protected to the author until the author releases the data (usually following publication).

In June and July of 2006 we employed two computer science undergraduates on research stipends to further develop MorphoBank. Both of these students were ethnic minorities, Steven Villaverde (a Latino) and Philomey Charles (an African American). These students added online tutorial movies to the site that show new users many of the features of the site. Secondly, they developed a dynamic FAQ database that can be expanded and edited by site administrators. Finally they created a database of active programs for administrators to see the status of ongoing projects.

We have added a labeling feature to the site that allows cells in matrices to be automatically labeled with the character name and give character states. These labels are zoomable with the images and permit an extremely explicit record of homology statements.”

Publication:

“We are happy to report that MORPHOBANK will be featured in a review article in the December issue of Trends in Ecology and Evolution, 2006 (authors De Queiroz and Gatesy).

Appendix A.10.

Demographics of NESCent Sponsored Groups – Gender and Country of Residence

Appendix A.12.

Home Institution Type - Sabbatical Scholars and Postdoctoral Fellows

Appendix A.13.

Attendees at NESCent Meetings by State December 1, 2005 – November 30, 2006

State	Code	Total	Female	Male	State	Code	Total	Female	Male	State	Code	Total	Female	Male	State	Code	Total	Female	Male
Arizona	AZ	4	2	2	Iowa	IA	4	1	3	New Hampshire	NH	1	0	1	Puerto Rico		4	1	3
California	CA	33	12	21	Kansas	KS	4	1	3	New Jersey	NJ	4	1	3	South Dakota	SD	5	4	1
Colorado	CO	3	0	3	Louisiana	LA	6	0	6	New Mexico	NM	1	0	1	Tennessee	TN	1	0	1
Connecticut	CT	7	0	7	Maryland	MD	4	1	3	New York	NY	21	8	13	Texas	TX	6	2	4
Florida	FL	9	1	8	Massachusetts	MA	7	1	6	North Carolina	NC	40	13	27	Virginia	VA	2	1	1
Georgia	GA	6	2	4	Michigan	MI	2	0	2	Ohio	OH	8	0	8	Washington DC	DC	4	1	3
Illinois	IL	10	0	10	Minnesota	MN	1	0	1	Oregon	OR	5	2	3	Wyoming	WY	1	0	1
Indiana	ID	6	2	4	Missouri	MO	12	4	8	Pennsylvania	PA	9	2	7	Total		230	62	168

Appendix A.14.

Attendees at NESCent Meetings by Country of Residence December 1, 2005 – November 30, 2006

Country	Total	Female	Male	Country	Total	Female	Male
Canada	7	2	5	Madagascar	1	0	1
Dominican Republic	1	0	1	Panama	1	0	1
Finland	1	0	1	Portugal	1	0	1
France	4	2	2	Sweden	1	0	1
Germany	1	0	1	The Netherlands	1	0	1
Israel	1	0	1	UK	6	2	4
Jamaica	1	0	1	<i>US</i>	230	62	168
Japan	2	0	2	<i>Non-US</i>	29	6	23
				Total	259	68	191

Appendix A.15.

NESCent Representation at Meetings December 1, 2005 – November 30, 2006

Outreach Activities by NESCent Directors and Staff

Greg Gibson

- University of North Carolina at Pembroke, Pembroke, NC, January 2006
- SCST: Society of College Science Teachers workshop, part of MSTA (National Science Teachers Association) Annual Meeting, Anaheim, CA, April 2006
- University of Agadir, Morocco, and International Foundation for Conservation of Desert Wildlife, Agadir, Morocco, December 2006

Josh Granek

- Collaborative Research Experience for Undergraduates, Norfolk State University, Norfolk, VA, July 2006

Kristin Jenkins

- AIBS Council Meeting/Annual Meeting, Washington, DC, May 2006
- SSE Education Committee, Evolution 2006, Stony Brook, NY, June 2006
- AIBS Education Committee Meeting, Washington, DC, August 2006

Joel Kingsolver

- Society of Comparative and Integrative Biology, Orlando, FL, January 2006
- Society for the Study of Evolution, Stony Brook, NY, June 2006

Hilmar Lapp

- Evolution 2006, Stony Brook, NY, June 2006
- ESA Data Registry Workshop, Washington, DC, July 2006
- Bioinformatics Open Source Conference 2006, Fortaleza, Brazil, August 2006
- Information Integration Workshop, Philadelphia, PA, October 2006

Kathleen Smith

- AIBS Board Meeting, Washington, DC, May 2006
- Evolution Meeting, Stony Brook, NY, May 2006
- Public Science Fair, Toy Challenge (Sigma Xi), RTP, NC, May 2006 (with Kristin Jenkins, Patricia Gensel, and Samantha Price)
- Ecological Society of America, Society Summit-Data Sharing, Washington, DC, July 2006
- Workshop on Leadership in Science Sponsored by NSF Advance Program, Logan, UT, September 2006
- NABT Symposium Sponsored by NESCent & AIBS, Albuquerque, NM, October 2006

Todd Vision

- NSF RCN (Deep Gene) Sponsored Workshop on Ontology & Phylogeny, St. Louis, MO, May 2006
- Evolution 2006 (Annual Meeting of SSE/SSB/ASN), Stony Brook, NY, June 2006
- The role of academic libraries in the digital data universe, NSF workshop, September 2006

Jory Weintraub

- Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS), Tampa, FL, October 2006
- University of Puerto Rico at Rio Piedras and Humacao, Puerto Rico, November 2006

Jory Weintraub & Kristin Jenkins

- National Science Teachers Association (NSTA), NCEAS, and University of California Museum of Paleontology, Anaheim, CA, April 2006
- National Association of Biology Teachers, Albuquerque, NM, October 2006
- North Carolina Science Teachers Association (NCSTA), Greensboro, NC, November 2006

Participation in Scientific MeetingsDoug Eernisse

- Western Society of Naturalists, Redmond, WA, November 2006

Kirsten Fisher

- NSF RCN (Deep Gene) Sponsored Workshop on Ontology & Phylogeny, St. Louis, MO, May 2006
- “Moss 2006” and Physcomitrella Genome Annotation Workshop, June 2006

Patricia Gensel

- Advances in Paleobotany Meeting, Gainesville, FL, March 2006
- Future Research Directions in Paleontology, Washington, DC, April 2006
- Botanical Society of America, Chico, CA, July 2006
- European Palaeobotanical and Palynology Conference, Prague, Czech Republic, September 2006
- Geological Society of America Annual Meeting, Philadelphia, PA, October 2006

Greg Gibson

- Annual Drosophila Meeting, Houston, TX, April 2006

Josh Granek

- Models of Co-Evolution of Hosts and Pathogens, New York City, NY and New Brunswick, NJ, October 2006

Joe Hereford

- JCBR Molecular Workshop, Gainesville, FL, April 2006
- SSE-Evolution 2006, Stony Brook, NY, June 2006
- AGA Annual Symposium, Vancouver, BC Canada, July 2006

Jason Hoeksema

- 5th International Conference on Mycorrhizas, Granada, Spain, July 2006

David Kidd

- GIS Research UK 2006. Annual Conference of UK GIS Researchers, Nottingham, UK, April 2006
- Paleogeography and Palaeobiogeography: Biodiversity in Space and Time, National Institute for Environmental Science, Center for Mathematical Sciences, Cambridge, UK, April 2006
- Evolution 2006, Stony Brook, NY, June 2006
- GMOD Meeting, NESCent, Durham, NC, June 2006

Samantha Price

- “Mammal Consortium,” Zoological Society of London, Institute of Zoology, London Zoo, UK, March 2006
- Science Society of Vertebrate Paleontology, Symposium on the Early Radiation of the Neoceti, Ottawa, Ontario, October 2006

Derrick Zwickl

- SSE/SSB Meeting (Evolution), Stony Brook, NY, June 2006
- Marine Biological Laboratory, Workshop on Molecular Evolution, Woods Hole, MA, August 2006

APPENDIX B. 1

PROCEDURES FOR ESTABLISHING INFORMATICS PRIORITIES

From The Revised Informatics Plan, February, 2006

As ideas for cyberinfrastructure initiatives emerge from the community they will be evaluated and prioritized based on explicit criteria. The criteria by which future initiatives are to be evaluated and prioritized include:

- The strength of commitment among the evolutionary biology community.
- The anticipated impact on facilitating evolutionary synthesis.
- The disciplinary diversity of the scientific communities that are affected.
- Feasibility and cost-effectiveness.
- The strength of the match to the informatics capabilities of the center.
- The extent to which the success of the initiative would depend on the participation of the center.

An Informatics Advisory Committee (IAC) will help the Associate and Assistant Directors for Informatics evaluate technical aspects of the proposals when appropriate. Collectively, the group is intended to have practical experience in diverse aspects of evolutionary informatics and related disciplines (e.g. integrative biology, ecology, genomics, molecular evolution, paleontology, population genetics, and systematics). Members of the group are also being selected for their ability to act as liaisons to different constituencies that will be important in developing major cyberinfrastructure initiatives. We expect this group to be fairly fluid in membership, and anticipate adding other members to round out the diversity of the committee and add expertise as new informatics opportunities arise.

This group will function as a technical advisory group, and will not be responsible for award decisions. It will assist the Associate Director for Informatics in assessing the feasibility of potential projects, prioritizing initiatives and developing specific strategies for implementations. Decisions about NESCent's participation in any major cyberinfrastructure initiatives will be made by the Operations Committee in consultation with the Senior Advisory Board.

NESCENT INFORMATICS

ORGANIZATIONAL CHART

Organizational chart of the NESCent informatics staff. This chart shows the individuals funded off the core funding; those that will be added if pending grants are funded as well as the administrative/IT staff assistant.

IT Support Policy

1. Purpose / Background

This document applies to Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, Working Groups, and Catalysis Meetings at NESCent. Collectively these are referred to as 'sponsored science' or 'sponsored scientists'. The document outlines the range of IT and informatics support NESCent can provide so as to ensure that the needs and expectations of sponsored scientists align with NESCent's informatics resources and capabilities.

NESCent's finite IT resources must be allocated to a large number of different projects, so if, as a sponsored scientist, you anticipate that human, software, or hardware resource needs may go beyond the basic level of IT support, please contact the Associate Director for Informatics (Todd Vision, tjv@bio.unc.edu, 919-843-4507) to discuss your needs.

2. Hardware Resources

2.1 Computer Hardware

NESCent provides shared workstations for use by resident scientists as well as meeting and working group participants. The machine(s) can be booted into either a Mac OSX or Windows operating system, and is equipped with a variety of office productivity and basic evolutionary analysis software.

For high-performance computing, sponsored scientists can be granted access to the Duke Shared Cluster Resource (<http://www.csem.duke.edu/Cluster/>), on which NESCent maintains a number of priority nodes and a variety of installed software packages. Sponsored scientists who anticipate using the cluster should notify support@nescent.org at least 3 weeks in advance of when it is needed.

NESCent can also provide loaner PC and Macintosh laptops for visitors on site. Sponsored scientists who anticipate using loaner laptops should register their need in advance at support@nescent.org to allow reservation of the equipment.

2.2 Office Hardware

NESCent maintains shared and fully networked common office devices, like color and b/w printers, copier, scanner, and fax. Instructions on how to use these will be communicated to meeting participants and incoming fellows prior to or at the start of a meeting or fellowship.

2.3 Network

All offices, conference rooms, and break-out spaces are covered by 802.11g-compatible wi-fi wireless network access points. Offices and conference rooms also have wall jacks for wired Ethernet network access. Instructions on how to use the network will be communicated to meeting participants and incoming fellows prior to or at the start of a meeting or fellowship.

2.4 A/V Equipment

NESCent has several video projectors with at least 1024x768 resolution. Projectors are provided for meetings, and resident scientists may use them as needed. The center also maintains audio and videoconferencing equipment ('Polycom') for use by all sponsored scientist. Sponsored scientists who anticipate using the A/V conferencing equipment should register their need in advance at support@nescent.org to allow reservation of the equipment. NESCent IT will assist in setup as needed.

3. Software And Application Infrastructure

3.1 Hosting Services Environment

NESCent maintains an environment for hosting collaborative sites, mailing lists, databases, web-applications, and source code development. In particular, NESCent runs the following services.

Apache-based web server

PHP4 (apache-module based) and PHP5 (cgi-based)

JBoss application server (for J2EE/EJB applications), including Tomcat (for JSP/Servlet applications)

MySQL 4.x and PostgreSQL 8.x relational database management systems

Subversion source code repository

Mailman for managing mailing lists

MediaWiki for electronic collaborative workspaces

Gallery for photo albums

IT will assist sponsored scientists to use these services on an as-needed basis. Contact support@nescent.org to allow NESCent proper planning and allocation of resources.

3.2 Scientific Software

Sponsored scientists should communicate their anticipated needs for analysis software to support@nescent.org as early as possible to allow time for licensing and setup, especially for software needed on the high-performance compute cluster. NESCent IT acquires, installs, and, where necessary, licenses scientific software on resident scientists' workstations, on shared workstations, and on the high-performance compute cluster.

3.3 Collaborative Tools And Workspace

To facilitate effective electronic communication, sharing of documents, discussion notes, reports, slide presentations, and other material, NESCent Informatics sets up a mailing list and deploys a Wiki-type electronic collaborative workspace for all working groups. The electronic workspace is pre-loaded with content specific to the meeting participants, and a tutorial can be delivered to meeting participants on-site. Resident scientists can also request mailing lists and Wiki-type electronic workspaces to be set up for themselves and their collaborators.

4. Database And Application Development

NESCent Informatics staff can provide support in data modeling, database schema design and instantiation, and in programming middleware, web applications, and

stand-alone applications. The staff can also help with developing analysis workflows and scripts. Supported platforms include:

Programming languages: C, C++, Java, Perl, PHP4, R

Database platforms: PostgreSQL

Statistics platforms: R

Web application platforms: PHP, J2EE (JSP, JSTL, Servlets)

Middleware platforms: EJB, Hibernate, Spring

Stand-alone GUI applications: Java/Swing

GIS programming: ArcGIS

NESCent Informatics can provide consulting and limited development time in support of sponsored science. Scientific visitors who anticipate requiring application, database, or workflow development in support of their project should contact Todd Vision (tjv@bio.unc.edu), preferably before accepting their award, to discuss how to meet their needs.

In order to maximize the number of sponsored scientists whose needs the programming staff can support, NESCent's Informatics team will typically only aim to develop prototype, rather than production-level, databases and web interfaces. If accomplishing the research goals of a funded proposal requires an enterprise-scale production-type system, NESCent will assist in applying for the appropriate support at the San Diego Supercomputing Center's Data Central, or in submitting a grant application to support additional software development staff.

National Evolutionary Synthesis Center

2024 W. Main St., Suite A200

Durham, NC 27705 USA

<http://www.nescent.org>

919-668-4551

Data and Software Policy

Introduction

NESCent strongly believes that sharing all data and software source code with the research community is a key ingredient towards fostering synthetic research at NESCent and elsewhere, and therefore contributes to advancing evolutionary science as a whole.

In order to accomplish its mission, and to best support the scientific community in advancing evolutionary science as a discipline, NESCent expects that all data and software created through NESCent-sponsored activities be made publicly available.

Scope

This document defines the policies for sharing data and software source code that is created, generated, used, hosted, replicated, sponsored, or made available by a NESCent-sponsored scientist, project, or activity, or by a collaboration in which NESCent participates.

In the remainder of this document data and software source code within the scope of this policy is collectively referred to as NESCent-sponsored data and software source code, respectively.

Data or software used that have more restrictive terms of use and dissemination than those set forth here are exempt from this policy. However, NESCent strongly encourages its participants and collaborators to consider alternatives that do not restrict sharing and free dissemination.

NESCent-sponsored Data

NESCent is committed to making all evolutionary biology and any other data within the scope of this policy readily available to the broader scientific community.

To meet this goal, NESCent-sponsored data or datasets

- are to be accessible from a web-based interface, with no restrictions for use and dissemination, or at the choice of the principle investigator under a [Creative Commons](#) license or compatible terms of use,
- are to be made available in a timely manner, generally no later than one year after the conclusion of the NESCent award, or immediately upon publication of an associated article, whichever comes earlier, and are to be kept current, if they undergo continuing updates, and

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- are to be sufficiently documented using appropriate standards and conventions agreed upon by the evolutionary biology community, including registration and deposition at a public meta-data registry and data repository if such a registry or repository exist. This documentation must include appropriate acknowledgment and attribution of any data used from other researchers or sources, as required by the copyright, license, or terms of use of such data.

NESCent recognizes that there are many questions associated with the open licensing of scientific data collections and encourages sponsored scientists to familiarize themselves with the issues (<http://sciencecommons.org/data/dbfaq>).

NESCent-sponsored Software

NESCent is committed to open-source software development and distribution. Software developed with NESCent funding or participation is expected to become readily and freely available to the broader scientific community.

Specifically, NESCent-sponsored software

- is to be made accessible on a FTP or web-accessible site hosted by NESCent, or at [Sourceforge](http://sourceforge.net) (<http://sourceforge.net>) or a similar site, for download in source code, and the source code is to be licensed under a [OSI-approved Open Source license](http://www.opensource.org/licenses/) (<http://www.opensource.org/licenses/>)
- is to be made available in a timely manner, meaning as early as possible but no later than the termination of the collaboration or fellowship, or publication of an article involving the software or data generated using the software, whichever comes earlier, and
- is to be sufficiently documented, stating at a minimum purpose, copyright and license, and acknowledging and attributing any other software or software libraries that the NESCent-sponsored software uses or depends on, as required by the licenses of such software. Copyright and license must be stated in every source code file, and the licenses for all the files constituting the software must be compatible.

Support By NESCent IT

NESCent's Informatics team will help a principal investigator or NESCent fellow in selecting the most suitable Creative Commons or Open Source license, and placing the license appropriately on the website for the dataset or the software, as well as in depositing data, meta-data, and software source code in the pertinent public repository. NESCent and its Informatics team will also help to remove any obstacles towards making data and software available, for instance by researching and resolving license incompatibilities, consulting or coordinating with collaborators, etc.

Continuation of Support

NESCent Informatics will schedule a wrap-up meeting with all NESCent fellows about 3-4 weeks before their term at NESCent ends. The goal of this interview is to identify any data, data sets, and source code that the scientist created under NESCent support, and to develop a recommendation for what type of continued support NESCent should provide for the data or data collection (for instance, hosting a database) and for the software (e.g.,

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fielding user questions, bug resolution, or continued feature development). The recommendation will be communicated to the leaving scientist, at the latest upon approval by NESCent's Director.

NESCent is not positioned to guarantee hosting of a database or application for the long term. NESCent will, however, help to establish or secure such long-term hosting if recommended, for instance by assisting to apply to [DataCentral](#) at the [San Diego Supercomputer Center](#).

Copyright and Acknowledgment

Data or datasets, software, published books and scholarly articles generated or created by a NESCent fellow or through a project or meeting funded by NESCent must appropriately and conspicuously acknowledge NESCent and the National Science Foundation.

December 15, 2006 | Vol. 10 No. 48

NESCent Hosts Hackathon to Jumpstart Development of Phyloinformatics Toolkit

By
Bernadette
Toner

The National Evolutionary Synthesis Center, a National Science Foundation-funded center to promote multidisciplinary research in evolutionary biology, has enlisted the help of the bioinformatics open source software community to build a better set of phyloinformatics software tools.

This week, the center, known as NESCent, hosted a so-called hackathon with the goal of building the “glue” to link together disparate complex phylogenetic software programs into seamless workflows.

Around two dozen developers from around the world gathered at NESCent’s headquarters in Durham, NC, from Dec. 11 to Dec. 15. Participants included developers of phylogenetic software packages like HyPhy, CIPRES, and PAUP, as well as representatives of key bioinformatics open-source packages like BioPerl, BioJava, BioPython, and BioRuby.

The goal of the hackathon was to enhance the capabilities of the open-source toolkits to work with phylogenetic software packages. In particular, developers worked on improving support for Nexus, a file format used in many of the leading phylogenetic software packages, and on building data models for exchanging phylogenetic information.

Phyloinformatics faces considerable challenges compared to more established bioinformatics disciplines like genome informatics. There are hundreds of highly sophisticated phylogenetic software packages available — Joe Felsenstein of the University of Washington, the author of Phylip, has compiled a list of 282 phylogeny programs and 34 servers on his [website](#) — but little, if any, interoperability between those applications.

“There are many, many ways you can analyze your data, and therefore there is a huge opportunity for aligning these methods together into workflows or pipelines ... to ask really sophisticated questions,” said Hilmar Lapp, assistant director of informatics at NESCent.

However, Lapp added, “there is a high barrier of entry for people who aren’t experts with those tools ... because they use different formats for input and output, oftentimes their own idiosyncratic ones.” In addition, he said, “even the standards that do exist in the field are used in ways that make ready exchange of data very difficult or impossible.”

Lapp, who organized the hackathon, said the goal was to “step in and create essentially the glue code that languages like Perl have been classically good at, if you look at the genome projects.”

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NESCent was founded in 2004 with a five-year, \$15 million grant from the NSF as a collaboration between Duke University, North Carolina State University, and the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill. The “synthesis” in the center’s name applies to its emphasis on synthetic science, which relies on pulling together existing data to gain understanding about a particular field — in NESCent’s case, evolutionary biology.

The center has an informatics team of around six people that supports around two dozen researchers.

Todd Vision, associate director of informatics at NESCent, said that the center has a number of internal development projects underway, but noted that the phylogenomics hackathon “is probably the biggest effort we’ve made to date in this area.”

“To some extent, a lot of what’s going to be done here will be sort of invisible to the user, and that’s sort of the goal.”

Vision said that NESCent wanted to bring together “the two communities — the developers of the software, who are very sophisticated about the methods involved but haven’t had much experience writing the open source bioinformatics toolkits of this sort, and developers from BioPerl, BioJava, BioPython, and BioRuby — to add support for those particular kinds of software and the toolkits so that they can be strung together.”

The results of the hackathon will be available to end users in the form of more user-friendly analysis. “To some extent, a lot of what’s going to be done here will be sort of invisible to the user, and that’s sort of the goal,” Vision said. “To make it so that there’s not more that they’ll have to learn, but hopefully less that they’ll have to do in terms of understanding idiosyncratic formats and going out of one application to go into another to do analysis that requires more than one application.”

Lapp acknowledged that not all of the open source toolkits will provide full support for phyloinformatic workflows by the end of the week, “because they’re starting from vastly different levels.” BioPerl, for example, is much more mature than most of the other toolkits, but the hope is that “they’ll all significantly advance their level of integrating data models and data formats and interfaces to programs.”

Vision added that many projects begun this week will likely continue for some time. “There are a lot of things that have been identified as future needs,” he said, “and now we have the collaborations that have emerged from this to work on them in the future, so I’m sure that the hackathon in spirit will live on longer than this week.”

Further information on the hackathon is available on its [wiki site](#).

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Appendix C.1.

Comprehensive Report of EOG Activities

	Specific Activity	Target Audience	Outcome/Deliverable
Conferences	Booth and presentation at National Science Teachers Association/ Society of College Teachers (April, 2006)	K-16 Educators, national (11,077 in attendance)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • collaborations with other education and outreach groups
	Booth and symposium at National Association of Biology Teachers (October, 2006)	K-16 Educators, national (~1,100 attendees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • Collaborations • NABT CD - see the <i>NABT Symposium</i> below
	Booth at North Carolina Science Teachers Association (November 2006)	K-12 Educators, state (~1,100 attendees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • collaborations with other education and outreach groups
	Booth at American Indian Science and Engineering Society (November, 2005)	American Indian students (~1,500 attendees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity
	Booth and Panel Discussion Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans (November, 2006)	Native American and Chicano students and educators (~2,300 attendees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • collaborations with other groups, see <i>SACNAS Panel</i> below
	Booth and presentation at the Society for the Study of Evolution (June, 2006)	Evolutionary biologists from Society for the Study of Evolution (SSE), Society of Systematic Biologists (SSB) and American Society of Naturalists (ASN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • attended the education symposium • participation in the SSE Education Committee

	Booth and presentation at the American Institute of Biological Sciences Annual Meeting (May, 2006)	Scientists, educators, policy makers (~250 in attendance)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • collaborations with other groups • participation in the AIBS Education Committee
	American Association for the Advancement of Science (February, 2006)	K-12 Educators, scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attended special section on “Evolution on the Front Line”
Visiting Lectures	Greg Gibson, Associate Director EOG – UNC, Pembroke	Undergraduates (~40 under-graduates)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture and meeting with biology faculty
	Paul Lewis, Sabbatical Scholar – North Carolina School for Science and Math	High School Juniors and Seniors (~20)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture
	Josh Granek, post-doctoral fellow – Norfolk State	Minority Undergraduates (~15)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture and meeting with students
Post-Doctoral Professional Development Program	<p>Series of lectures on the scholarship of teaching and learning</p> <p>Session 1: Learning Theories, Learning Styles</p> <p>Session 2: Critical Thinking and the Nature of Science</p> <p>Session 3: Planning Your First Course</p> <p>Session 4: Engaging Students: Active Learning, Case Based Learning, and Other Methods</p> <p>Session 5: Student Involvement: Group Projects, Self-Directed Learning and Learning Communities</p> <p>Session 6: Teaching With Technology, Teaching Via VTC</p> <p>Session 7: Testing, Assessment and Grading</p> <p>Session 8: Classroom Management, Dealing With Difficult Students</p> <p>Session 9: Diversity in the Classroom</p>	Postdoctoral Fellows (13 NESCent postdocs, ~14 additional attendees (other postdocs and grad students from Duke, UNC, etc.), ~10 sabbatical scholars, ADs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture series
	<p>Career development sessions</p> <p>“Applying for Faculty Positions in Evolution”</p> <p>“Media Training for Scientists”</p> <p>“The Duke Office of Postdoctoral Services (OPS) and Duke University Postdoc Association (DUPA)”</p>	Postdoctoral Fellows (13 NESCent postdocs, ~14 additional attendees (other postdocs and grad students from Duke, UNC, etc.), ~10 sabbatical scholars, ADs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations • resources for post-docs

Web Site	Develop novel content and compile resources (http://eog.nescent.org)	K-16 Educators (>6,000 hits Jan-Nov 2006)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evolution in the News articles • links to various resources • distribution of information about evolutionary biology and NESCent
	J.Clamp's sabbatical project "Bringing Together MSIs and Evolution Graduate and Research Programs" (http://eog.nescent.org/Databases.htm)	Minority students, mentors, and graduate recruiters	Database of contacts at minority serving institutions, and complimentary database of graduate programs in evolutionary biology
Publications	Interview "Kathleen K. Smith: Integrating the Levels of Evolution", T. Beardsley, 2006, <i>BioScience</i> , Vol 56(6), p470	Scientific Community (monthly circulation ~7,000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity, awareness of NESCent's programs
	Evolutionary Biologists Aim to Protect Madagascar's Plants and Animals, M.R. Robertson, 2006, <i>ActionBioscience</i> , http://www.actionbioscience.org/evolution/roberson.html	K-16 Educators and students (~ 1,000,000 site hits in 2005)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • access to scientific activities at NESCent
	Brochures, booth display	Scientific community, Education community, general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity, awareness of NESCent's programs
	Macroevolution essay accepted at <i>The American Biology Teacher</i>	4-16 Biology Teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity for NESCent • awareness of NABT evolution symposium • resources for teachers
NESCent scientific activities	Attendance at working groups and catalysis meetings	Scientific community, general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader impact consultations • Publications • web based summaries, liaison activities
Outreach	Panel at SACNAS: "Exploring Careers in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology"	Minority students and mentors (~ 40 to 50 attendees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants requested that activity be repeated annually, plan to collaborate with ESA, NCEAS, SSE and AIBS for 2007

	Educational resources for the 2006 NABT Evolution Symposium “Macroevolution”(http://eog.nescent.org/NABTsymposia.htm)	High school and college educators (871 CDs distributed in USA and Canada)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 500 CDs distributed at the conference • additional CDs distributed at other conferences in Canada and USA • content also available online
	Booth at TOYChallenge	National middle school students (focusing on girls), teachers, parents (~900 student attendees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity • promotion of evolutionary science
EOG Working groups	Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU)	Faculty from minority serving institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See narrative
	Evolution Education		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See narrative

Report of the Senior Advisory Board of NESCent

April 14-15 2006

Overall Impressions

NESCent has recently undergone an administrative change with Dr. Kathleen Smith taking over the directorship from Dr. Cliff Cunningham. In addition, Dr. Todd Vision has been named Associate Director of Informatics and RENCI has withdrawn from NESCent. The new administrative team of NESCent is an extremely talented group that works well together and shares the goal of making NESCent a national leader in evolutionary biology. The SAB was impressed with Kathleen Smith's careful, thorough, and equitable approach to administration. We feel that NESCent is now poised to make rapid progress and to assume its role in setting the direction for evolutionary research and synthesis in the United States.

The new facilities for NESCent have been completed and are both beautiful and highly functional. The Center has ample room for offices, meetings and spaces for informal conversation, and it is configured to enhance interactions among post-docs, sabbatarians and visitors.

The administrative turnover has necessarily resulted in some lost time, as the new administration became familiar with the organization, administration and budgets of NESCent. In particular the IT component has lost about 6 months, due to the withdrawal of RENCI. We feel that this hiatus should be noted by NSF and accommodations made in the evaluation of NESCent, and/or in extending the grant. The SAB feels that the Director and Associate Directors have a clear vision and set of goals that are appropriate for NESCent.

Science and Synthesis

The first cohort of post-docs and sabbatarians has arrived at the center. The quality of this first group is very high and bodes well for fulfilling NESCent's goal of serving as a national center and a think-tank for new ideas. Individual's comments regarding NESCent were uniformly positive and enthusiastic. Several working groups and catalysis meetings have been convened and by all accounts were highly successful. Cliff Cunningham introduced the concept of catalysis groups; they have proven to be especially productive brainstorming sessions and we urge that they be retained, rather than phased out after one year as originally planned.

Many of the concerns from our previous visit about the timing of proposal deadlines and the number of applicants have been resolved. NESCent is developing a mentoring program to address our previous concern that all post docs receive adequate advice and scientific interactions. As NESCent becomes increasingly active, it will be important to maintain flexibility in the science and synthesis program, so that NESCent can quickly respond to creative new ideas. We suggest NESCent consider more flexible patterns for funding sabbaticals and visiting fellows (e.g., not restrict these visits to full or half year visits), and we encourage many

different kinds of working groups and collaborations. However, in summary, the SAB felt that the Science and Synthesis component of NESCent was off to a very strong start and that programs were on the correct trajectory. The goals set for Science and Synthesis are appropriate and reachable.

Education and Outreach Group

The education and outreach program in the first year has been very productive, and has laid the foundation for the next four years. As was noted in our previous visit, the education and outreach goals were very broad and needed to be prioritized. The activities have now been focused to address “broader impacts,” rather than in-reach. A real strength of the EOG is the staff’s dedication and commitment to education and outreach. The EOG has already many accomplishments including developing and launching a website, attending and developing various working groups, developing curriculum modules, and participation at many education conferences as well as sponsoring evolution symposia at the National Association of Biology Teachers annual meeting. The web site for the EOG is excellent. Among several other things, we were impressed with the weekly updates of significant discoveries in evolutionary biology delivered in clear simple prose for easy accessibility by the lay public. We believe the EOG group is making good progress but we feel that it is important that they continue to focus their efforts and develop a strategic plan to most effectively use their resources. In particular we believe they should focus their efforts more on promoting and translating the science at NESCent to the broader scientific community and to the general public.

One issue that came to our attention was the relationship between NESCent and AIBS. AIBS has a strong focus on science policy with many activities in Washington. At the present time NESCent’s interest in education and outreach are focused more on education than on policy. It is not clear that NESCent should be involved with policy, given its limited resources. The role that AIBS plays in Education and Outreach should be clarified.

Computational Infrastructure

A strong team has been assembled in this area, led by Dr. Todd Vision. The role of this group has now been focused to serve the specific in-house needs of NESCent, providing IT support for the staff, visitors and scientists. One of the original aims of NESCent was to be a major innovator in terms of computation and informatics. At the time of our previous visit it was not clear that the portals that were being developed by RENCI were directly serving NESCent. We feel that the new team is setting appropriate goals for IT at NESCent.

There is a clear need for national level coordination of databases and informatics for evolutionary biology and NESCent is an appropriate and logical site for such work. Such a role was part of the original grant and core funding from NSF. However, the SAB is concerned that NESCent may not be able to fulfill this role on the core grant alone. There are several efforts at

NESCent to coordinate databases and several working groups have focused on informatics. In addition, NESCent plans a number of national initiatives as well. The experience of NCEAS has demonstrated that a major role in national informatics will require additional funding. The informatics staff at NESCent is currently planning several proposals, and the SAB concurs that such efforts are necessary for NESCent to fulfill this goal.

The SAB thought that the IT section might set up an informatics meeting to help sort through all of the possible activities that are currently under consideration. A catalysis group comprised of stakeholders drawn from a broad range of informatics perspectives would help set priorities for NESCent that are consistent with the needs of the evolution community.

Other Issues

Senior Advisory Board: The SAB felt strongly that it should serve as an advisory board to NESCent as opposed to a board focused on critical review or evaluation. We felt that it would compromise our ability to advise NESCent if we also served as a review committee. It is clearly important to have regular full-scale review of NESCent, but a separate committee should be convened by NSF for that specific purpose.

The SAB also felt that it would be appropriate for the members of the SAB have terms, which ultimately would be staggered. This would reduce the amount of time that SAB members would have to commit (originally the SAB members were to serve 5 years) making it more likely that individuals would serve on the SAB. And it would insure that new views and expertise were added to the board when needed. We also feel that the Chair of the SAB should be rotated among the SAB members.

Another issue which requires clarification is potential conflicts of interest between SAB and NESCent. The SAB was concerned that some exciting ideas for catalysis meetings or workshops might not be realized if SAB members were barred from proposing or participating in these meetings. The SAB suggests that proposing workshops or other meetings for NESCent not be considered a conflict of interest and that proposals that happen to come from SAB members be weighed and potentially accepted or rejected on their merits just as other proposals would be evaluated.

Time Commitments of Director and Associate Directors: The SAB expressed some concern about the time demands on the senior administrative staff. There is a great deal to do, and all of the individuals serve part time while continuing with their own University careers. One worries that they will have enough time to adequately address both NESCent and their other duties, particularly as NESCent becomes more active. One possibility would be to recruit a full-time director in the same way that NCEAS has done. Recruiting a full time director would have the advantage of bringing to NESCent an individual that is 100% focused on the life of NESCent. While Kathleen Smith is clearly doing an outstanding, admirable, and high quality

job, there is no substitute for a director who is focused solely on NESCent without the duties of a separate academic career. Another advantage of seeking a full time Director is that the individual would not necessarily need to be at Duke. A national search would identify a candidate that is best suited for this position.

Short Term Goals:

Given the recent administrative change, the SAB thought it would be important to establish some metrics of success for NESCent. Within the next 2.5 years, one could reasonably expect NESCent to complete most of the following:

- a full complement of postdoctoral fellows and sabbatarians
- a vibrant series of workshops and catalysis meetings
- a NESCent Website that is informative, accessible, and which serves as a resource to the evolution community
- an evolution community list-server for NESCent's use
- three additional senior advisory board meetings
- increased outreach to the evolution community, including a program of presentations to
 - scientific societies at annual meetings and hosting board meetings of the major evolutionary biology societies
- interactions with NCEAS in areas of overlap (consider joint workshops, etc)
- IT in-house support up and running including both administrative and high performance computing
- develop a focus for IT
- submit proposals to support major initiatives
- assume a leading role in developing metadata and data registries for evolutionary biology
- develop tighter focus for the EOG group, including the Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEMU) Program

Appendix D.2.				
NESCent Scheduled Meetings - December 2006 - August 2007				
November 30 - December 5, 2006	Kalisz, Susan Johnston, Mark	Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating in Flowering Plants	10	Work Group
December 5, 2006	Lapp, Hilmar	Digital Repository of Information and Data for Evolution (DRIADE) Workshop	12	Informatics
December 8, 2006	Greenburg, Jane	"Metadata Architectures and Applications," School of Information and Library Science, Metadata Research Center, UNC-CH	16	Class
December 10-15, 2006	Lapp, Hilmar	First NESCent Phyloinformatics Hackathon	20	Informatics
December 12-14, 2006	Jungck, John Weosstein, Anton E.	Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in ACTION	12	Work Group
December 16 - 19, 2006	Uyenoyama, Marcy Tokuta, Alade Nielsen, Rasmus	Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression (December 18 & 19 at NESCent)		Triangle Work Group
January 4 - 6, 2007	Carter, Pat	Evolution of Function-Valued Traits	35	Hosted
January 12 - 14, 2007	Macaluso, Andrea	Springer Editorial Board Meeting	10	Hosted
January 15 - 16, 2007	NSF	National Science Foundation Site Visit	?	Site Visit
February 1 - 5, 2007	Payne, Jonathan Stempien, Jennifer Kowalewski, Michael	Phanerozoic body size trends in time and space: macroevolution and macroecology	12	Work Group
February 1 - 2, 2007	Kingsolver, Joel	Scientific Advisory Board	15	Advisory
March 5 - 9, 2007	Lapp, Hilmar	Digital Repositories for Published Scientific Data	?	Informatics
March 11-15, 2007	Donoghue, Michael Manos, Paul	Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere	15	Work Group
March 12 -16, 2007	Bergman, Casey Keitman, Martin Dermitzakis, Manolis	Synthesizing Computational Resources for Cis-regulatory Molecular Evolution.	12	Work Group
March 16 - 18, 2007	Simon, Chris	Society for Systematic Biologists	10	Hosted
March 18 - 21, 2007	Zanne, Amy	NESCent Joint Australia Meeting, Group 1	12	Co-Sponsored
March 20 - 23, 2007	Zanne, Amy	NESCent Joint Australia Meeting, Group 2	12	Co-Sponsored
March 22 - 25, 2007	Zanne, Amy	NESCent Joint Australia Meeting, Group 3	12	Co-Sponsored
March 31 - April 4, 2007	Kocher, Tom	Genomic Approaches to the Study of Adaptive Radiation	30	Catalysis
April 18 - 21, 2007	Schindel, David	AToL/CBOL Meeting	30	Hosted
April 20 - 24, 2007	Cracraft, Joel Siddall, Mark	Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography	14	Work Group
April 23 - 28, 2007	Peet, Bob	Toward an international exchange standard for vegetation and biodiversity co-occurrence data	10	Hosted
April 26 - May 2, 2007	Lapp, Hilmar Vision, Todd	Possible Informatics Meeting (or May 4 - 10, 2007)	20	NESCent
May 1 - 5, 2007	Hughes, Kim Breden, Felix Weigel, Detlef	Developing New Model Systems for Evolutionary Genomics Using Poeciliid Fishes	30	Catalysis
May 4 - 10, 2007	Lapp, Hilmar Vision, Todd	Possible Informatics Meeting (or April 26 - May 2, 2007)	20	NESCent
May 23 - 26, 2007 (Memorial Day Weekend)	Govindaraju, Raju Byers, Peter Stearns, Stephen	Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations: Medical, Genetic and Behavioral Implications	30	Catalysis
June 4 - 8, 2007	Plotnick, Roy	Origins and Evolution of Chemoreception	30	Catalysis
Summer 2007	Piel, William Vision, Todd	Phyloinformatics Summer Course (2 week course)	20	Class
August 9 - 13, 2007	Alberts, Susan Strier, Karen Wright, Patricia	Primate Life Histories	12	Work Group
Pending, (possibly March, 2007)	Noor, Mohamed Servideo, Maria	Proposal to Develop a Novel Journal Concept for Evolutionary Meta-Analyses	10	Work Group
Pending	Magwene, Paul Houle, David	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks	12	Work Group
Pending, (possibly May, 2007)	Stoltzfus, Arlin Vos, Rutger	Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis	12	Work Group
Pending	Gould, Fred Sinkins, Steven Hartl, Daniel	Selfish DNA and the genetic control of vector-borne diseases	30	Catalysis

NESCent Organizational Chart

